

From Snapshots to Manifolds: A Practical Roadmap For Interpolatory Reduced-Order Modeling

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SUBMISSION: "From Snapshot to Manifolds: A Practical Roadmap for Interpolatory Reduced-Order Modelling" – Review Article

Dear Professor,

I am writing to submit our manuscript titled "From Snapshot to Manifolds: A Practical Roadmap for Interpolatory Reduced-Order Modelling" for consideration in *Proceedings of the Royal Society A*. The work is authored by Ing. Giannikos Komis, Dr.-Ing. Swarup K. Barman, Prof. Dr.-Ing. Alessandro Astolfi, Prof. Dr.-Ing. Dimitrios Chronopoulos and myself.

In this paper, we introduce a unified framework for interpolation-based Reduced-Order Models (ROMs). We break down the growing research in this area into a simple six-stage workflow, complete with computational cost estimates and implementation-ready pseudocode. Our goal is to make these methods easier to understand and apply, helping them reach a wider audience in the computational mechanics community. We believe this makes the article a strong fit for the readers of the journal.

Highlights:

- Introduces a new taxonomy and historical overview of interpolation-based ROMs, spanning classic snapshot methods to advanced manifold techniques, all unified under a common algebraic framework.
- Provides both qualitative and quantitative performance comparisons across standard benchmarks and traditional projection-based ROM approaches.
- Offers practical guidelines on stabilization, sampling, and certification strategies to help practitioners choose and adapt the most suitable ROM for their needs.

We have obtained a formal agreement from the Reviews Editor for this submission; along with an extended page-limit of 40 pages (attached with this letter). The manuscript is original, has not been published elsewhere, and is not under review by any other journal. All authors have approved the submission and declare no conflicts of interest.

We appreciate your consideration of our submission and eagerly await your feedback. Should you require any further information or clarification, please do not hesitate to contact us.

Sincerely,

Dr.-Ing. Abhilash Sreekumar

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From: proceedingsa <proceedingsa@royalsociety.org>

Sent: Friday, October 3, 2025 4:06 PM

To: Abhilash Sreekumar <abhilash.sreekumar@kuleuven.be>

Subject: RE: Inquiry Regarding Suitability of Review Paper: "From Snapshots to Manifolds: A Practical Roadmap for Interpolatory Reduced-Order Modeling"

Dear Abhi,

Many thanks for your patience while we assessed your proposal.

The Review Editors have now considered your proposal and would be happy to receive a Review from you for possible consideration in the journal entitled 'From Snapshots to Manifolds: A Practical Roadmap for Interpolatory Reduced-Order Modeling'. Please visit our website for guidance on how to complete your submission <https://royalsocietypublishing.org/rspa/reviews>. Do note, your review will undergo rigorous peer review and there is no guarantee of acceptance.

If you are also able to provide an estimated date of submission, that would be appreciated. In addition, when you submit it would be most helpful if you could provide the names of some researchers you feel would be suitable to review your manuscript. We would ask that these suggestions have no conflict of interest and that you haven't co-published with them in the past 5 years. If you could provide the names of some suitable people that work in the area that would be most helpful and should speed up the review process.

Do let us know if you have any questions at this stage. We look forward to receiving your manuscript.

All the best,

Catherine

From: proceedingsa <proceedingsa@royalsociety.org>

Sent: Tuesday, October 7, 2025 6:14 PM

To: Abhilash Sreekumar <abhilash.sreekumar@kuleuven.be>

Subject: RE: Inquiry Regarding Suitability of Review Paper: "From Snapshots to Manifolds: A Practical Roadmap for Interpolatory Reduced-Order Modeling"

Dear Abhi,

The editor is happy to allow up to 40 pages. If you are able, please use the [Latex class file](#) so you can accurately estimate the number of pages your paper will take up in the Proceedings A format.

If you need anything else, then please let me know.

All the best,

Raminder

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MATHEMATICAL, PHYSICAL AND ENGINEERING SCIENCES

From Snapshots to Manifolds: A Practical Roadmap For Interpolatory Reduced-Order Modeling

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From Snapshots to Manifolds: A Practical Roadmap For Interpolatory Reduced-Order Modeling

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Interpolatory Reduced-Order Models (ROMs) rapidly approximate high-dimensional systems by constructing and blending low-order systems at selected interpolation points. This avoids repeated projection of full-order operators and yields orders-of-magnitude speed-ups, making these methods well-suited for real-time prediction, optimization, and control. Existing surveys examine individual techniques in isolation and employ advanced differential-geometric or system-theoretic formalisms, limiting accessibility to the broader engineering and computational communities.

In contrast, this review proposes a novel taxonomy categorizing all interpolation-based ROM families without cataloging every variant. For each family, the core mathematical ideas are conveyed through pseudocode and originally integrated into a unified six-stage workflow, accompanied by explicit $\mathcal{O}(\cdot)$ cost analyses. We then highlight key methodological extensions required for complex, real-world applications. A combined quantitative and qualitative assessment against six canonical benchmarks and traditional projection-based ROMs provides performance insights. The result is a practical roadmap enabling engineers and scientists to select, adapt, and deploy interpolation-based ROMs with clarity and assurance.

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Category	Goal	Content
Orientation	o New to interpolatory ROMs?	Table 2, Table 3
	o Need to pick the right method for your problem?	Table 5
	o Curious how interpolatory ROMs emerge from classical methods?	Figure 13
	o Need quick reference information?	Table 11, Table 12
Build/Analyse	o Want a recipe for your own interpolatory ROM?	Figure 9
	o Trying to understand computational cost?	Table 4
	o Interested in how each family performs on benchmarks?	Section 5
Implement/Deploy	o Looking for ready-to-use pseudocode?	<i>Supplementary Material</i>
	o Deciding which applications best fit your use case?	Table 8
	o Encountering numerical or stability issues?	Figure 16, Table 9

Table 1. How to Use This Review: A Practical Navigation Guide for Readers.

1. INTRODUCTION

High-fidelity simulations in computational mechanics and fluid dynamics often involve models with several millions of degrees of freedom (DoFs). When such models must be solved repeatedly within design loops, control frameworks, or uncertainty analyses, their computational cost becomes prohibitive even on modern high-performance computing (HPC) platforms [1, 2]. Model Order Reduction (MOR) aims to target this problem by projecting the governing equations onto a low-dimensional subspace that captures the dominant system behavior. The resulting reduced-order model (ROM) can reproduce the essential dynamics of the full-order model (FOM) at a fraction of the cost, while maintaining predictive accuracy within the trained parameter domain [1, 3, 4]. In most engineering applications, however, the system operators depend on parameters such as geometry, material coefficients, or operating conditions. Classical projection-based MOR methods, such as Proper Orthogonal Decomposition (POD) or Balanced Truncation (BT), typically construct a reduced basis at a fixed parameter point μ . Extending such models to parametric problems led to the development of *parametric MOR (pMOR) frameworks* [5–7]. These methods aim to reuse a common reduced basis across the parameter space, often by exploiting an affine or approximately affine decomposition of the relevant operators. This enables efficient online assembly through precomputed reduced matrices [8, 9]. However, this affine assumption is rarely satisfied exactly in complex, nonlinear, or geometrically varying systems, and constructing a single global basis that is accurate everywhere can require an impractically large reduced dimension.

To overcome these limitations, *interpolation-based ROM* emerged as a complementary paradigm. Instead of enforcing global affine decompositions, it builds a small set of local ROMs at discrete parameter points and blends them to predict new configurations. This strategy preserves the accuracy of local bases while avoiding repeated projection of full-order operators. Various interpolation schemes, ranging from simple spline fits [10] to differential-geometric formulations on Grassmann manifolds [11] have been proposed to ensure smooth transitions between reduced spaces without significantly affecting accuracy or stability. These methods are particularly attractive in contexts with strict online deadlines, such as aeroelastic control [12], structural optimization [13], or real-time digital twins [14]. Interpolation-based ROMs, therefore, bridge the gap between conventional projection-based MOR and data-driven surrogates. They combine the

Table 2. Overview of interpolation-based ROM families (T1–T7) introduced in this review.

ID	Family	Core idea	Typical use case
T1	POD / Snapshot-based projection	Global or local SVD bases of snapshots; interpolation of modal coefficients	Generic low-dimensional projection
T2	Transfer function / System matrix interpolation	Direct interpolation of reduced matrices or transfer functions in a common coordinate frame	Non-intrusive operator interpolation
T3	Gramian / Balanced-truncation	Lyapunov-based balancing with provable H_2 or H_∞ error bounds	Linear and stable systems
T4	Krylov / Interpolatory (moment-matching)	Rational or tangential interpolation using Krylov subspaces	Control and signal models
T5	Parameter-sampling and reduced-basis	Greedy sampling with certified residual-based error estimators	Parametric PDEs and uncertainty quantification
T6	Structure-preserving / Passive / Second-order	Energy, passivity, or symmetry-preserving reductions	Mechanical and electrical systems
T7	Manifold based interpolation of reduced bases	Log–exp mapping on Grassmann or Stiefel manifolds for smooth subspace interpolation	Nonlinear and multi-parametric ROMs

rigor of projection methods with the flexibility of non-intrusive interpolation; thereby offering physically realistic predictions throughout the parameter space without revisiting the costly snapshot-generation stage. Developing robust, efficient, and theoretically sound interpolation strategies has thus become a central theme in contemporary model reduction research, motivating the unified review presented in this work. A brief summary of the taxonomy and the methods that will be discussed throughout this paper can be found in Table 2.

(a) Historical Evolution (Pre-2012 to Present)

Figure 1. (a) Timeline of interpolation-based ROM families from inception to present, (b) Prevalence and interconnectedness of T1-T7.

Early interpolation-based reduced-order modeling arose in the 1990s and early 2000s within what are now called the **T1: Proper Orthogonal Decomposition / snapshot-based projection** and **T2: Transfer-function & System-Matrix Interpolation families (TM)** [15, 16]. The first studies fitted polynomial or spline functions to reduced coefficients or system responses to account for parameter changes [17, 18]. Direct interpolation of the basis vectors soon proved deficient; observations on orthogonality loss [19] showed that orthonormality can only be preserved by interpolating subspace angles [20]. This insight produced the subspace-angle interpolation approach [21, 22], an early geometric method later surveyed in [13, 23]. Although subspace-angle interpolation was successfully applied to aeroelastic domains [24], its pairwise nature hindered use with multiple parameters [25]. These ideas would eventually mature into the celebrated

manifold-based strategies (see *T7*) nearly ten years later. Contemporaneously, the Global POD (GPOD) strategy emerged from *T1* methods, enriching a single basis with snapshots from several parameter values. This proved effective when the snapshot ensemble adequately captured the influence of parameters. However, it failed when the variations were large. This was observed, for example, in transonic aeroelastic flow where the Mach number differed significantly from the design point [26–28]. In response, local ROM strategies emerged, representing an early form of the *T5: Parameter-sampling & Reduced-basis family (RB)* [29]. Separate reduced models were constructed at discrete points in the parameter space. Their modal coefficients or projected system matrices were then interpolated—often using cubic splines [19, 30]. It is worth noting that such approaches may also be classified under the *T2: Transfer-Function and System-Matrix Interpolation family* [15, 16].

During the same decade, the control systems and signal processing communities matured two additional families of methods. The *T4: Krylov / Interpolatory (moment-matching) family* arose from generalised Padé approximation and Lanczos algorithms to parametric systems [31–33], whereas the *T3: Gramian / balanced-truncation family* developed weighted- H_2 and Hankel-norm formulations with provable error bounds [16, 34]. These strands remained largely distinct from the POD-based work until the turn of the decade, when multiphysics applications began to couple them. A turning point occurred between 2008 and 2010, with the introduction of Grassmann-manifold interpolation [27, 35, 36]. By mapping each reduced basis to the tangent space of the Grassmann manifold and performing interpolation there, a new framework subsumed the subspace-angle ideas developed earlier and allowed any number of pre-computed bases to be combined while guaranteeing orthonormality [13, 23]. This innovation defined the modern *T7: Manifold-based Interpolation of Reduced Bases*. The same period saw further work on matrix-space interpolation and Riemannian splines [13] as well as continued refinement of spline and Kriging fits inside the *T2: Transfer-Function and System-Matrix Interpolation family* [37–39].

By 2012, aeroelastic research had converged on three principal paradigms: global basis enrichment via GPOD, direct interpolation of reduced vectors or matrices [40], and subspace-angle interpolation. Each of these, however, suffered from either prohibitive offline cost or limited robustness. The introduction of Grassmann-manifold interpolation provided a unified solution to the problem [41, 42]. This framework included several variants, such as the log–exp map, barycentric interpolation, and spline-based methods. It enabled near real-time predictions across varying Mach numbers. Instead of repeating the expensive snapshot–POD process, the method interpolated a compact database of ROMs [11, 43]. In the years that followed, methodological advances spread across all families of techniques. Greedy and sparse-grid snapshot selection revitalized *T5: Parameter-sampling and Reduced-basis* methods [31, 32], while low-rank, Riemannian and weighted- H_2 extensions enriched *T3: Gramian / Balanced-truncation* approaches [16, 34, 44]. In parallel, data-driven Loewner frameworks, which are traditionally associated with the *T2: Transfer-function and system-matrix interpolation family*, began to reinforce developments within both *T4: Krylov / Interpolatory (Moment-Matching)* and *T6: Structure-preserving, Passive, and Second-order Techniques* as well [32, 33, 45]. Dedicated interpolation schemes for bilinear, quadratic-bilinear and second-order systems then emerged, coupling nonlinear extensions to Grassmann and Loewner paradigms [13, 44]. The complete evolution of these techniques is summarized in Figure 1. A detailed *bibliographic review, highlighting the evolution of the field in terms of research output per method, can be found in the supplementary material of the publication.*

Novelty Statement: To date, *twenty six* dedicated review articles have surveyed interpolation-based MOR. These cluster into two distinct waves: (2004–2015) [15, 16, 31, 33, 34, 44–51]; and (2019–2024) [13, 52, 53]. Although these surveys are mathematically rigorous and comprehensive, their reliance on advanced differential-geometric and control-theoretic formalisms renders them largely inaccessible to a general engineering and computational audience. Moreover, no single review to date spans the gamut of interpolation ROMs, contrasts their foundational theories, unifies their algorithmic workflows, and delivers a quantitative cross-family benchmarking

framework. The present article fills this gap by (i) introducing the first comprehensive taxonomy of interpolation-based ROMs (T1–T7), accompanied by method-selection guidelines for practical deployment; (ii) providing core pseudocode templates and $\mathcal{O}(\cdot)$ complexity analyses within a unified construction workflow to facilitate implementation; (iii) establishing six canonical benchmark problems and associated performance metrics for both qualitative and quantitative evaluation; and (iv) outlining systematic mitigation strategies for the common pitfalls encountered across these interpolation families.

Remark 1: On Stability, Passivity, and Symplecticity

A system is considered *stable* when its response is bounded. If the response also decays towards an equilibrium point, then it can be considered to be asymptotically stable. For linear time-invariant (LTI) systems to be asymptotically stable, the eigenvalues of the state matrix need to have negative real parts. For general stability, simple (non-repeated) zero roots can also be allowed. *Passivity* refers to the system's energy dissipative nature; this means that the system cannot generate more energy than the input. Finally, systems with a *symplectic structure*, typically arising from Hamiltonian formulations, preserve the canonical form of the state space, and as a result they maintain energy and momentum with time propagation.

The structure of this review is as follows. [Section 2](#) delves into the theoretical foundations of T1-7 and reviews their state-of-the-art developments. Furthermore, [Section 3](#) distills T1-7 into a unified six-step recipe along with a cost analysis and method picker. [Section 4](#) examines recent methodological extensions incorporating the above techniques. [Section 5](#) provides a comprehensive comparative study and positions interpolation-based ROMs within the broader MOR landscape. [Section 6](#) and [Section 7](#) discuss applications and the associated challenges, respectively. Finally [Section 8](#) and [Section 9](#) outline emerging trends and future perspectives.

2. CORE THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS

The seven interpolation-based MOR families discussed in [Section 1\(a\)](#) encompass a broad spectrum of techniques, as detailed in [Figure 2](#). This list, though necessarily non-exhaustive, includes representative seminal/legacy and state-of-the-art methods along with relevant survey articles (provided in the sub-header of each family). Each family is now discussed in detail. We first develop the core mathematical formalism and summarize its key steps in algorithmic pseudocode (see *Supplementary material*). Then, we review related developments together with the intrinsic advantages and limitations of each approach. The following notational conventions are adopted

- the full-order model states $\mathbf{u}(t, \mu)$ have dimension n ,
- the observed outputs $\mathbf{y}(t, \mu)$ of the systems have dimension n_y ,
- the input vector $\mathbf{v}_{\text{in}}(t)$ has dimensions n_v ,
- the reduced order subspace has dimension $r \ll n$, and the reduced order operators are symbolized with $\hat{[\cdot]}$,
- m denotes a hyper-reduction sample size,
- the parameter vector is $\mu \in \mathcal{D} \subset \mathbb{R}^d$.

In the general case, the full-order system may be defined as

$$\mathbf{E}(\mu)\dot{\mathbf{u}}(t, \mu) = f(\mathbf{u}(t, \mu), \mathbf{v}_{\text{in}}(t), \mu, t), \quad (2.1)$$

$$\mathbf{y}(t, \mu) = g(\mathbf{u}(t, \mu), \mathbf{v}_{\text{in}}(t), \mu, t), \quad (2.2)$$

where f, g are general functions describing the system dynamics and output relations respectively. $\mathbf{E} \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ is called the descriptor matrix. Although most methods are, in principle,

extendable to general nonlinear systems, they are first introduced within LTI systems for clarity.

$$\mathbf{E}(\mu)\dot{\mathbf{u}}(t, \mu) = \mathbf{A}(\mu)\mathbf{u}(t, \mu) + \mathbf{B}(\mu)\mathbf{v}(t), \quad (2.3)$$

$$\mathbf{y}(t, \mu) = \mathbf{C}(\mu)\mathbf{u}(t, \mu) + \mathbf{D}(\mu)\mathbf{v}(t), \quad (2.4)$$

where the descriptor, system, input, output, and feed-through matrices, \mathbf{E} , \mathbf{A} , \mathbf{B} , \mathbf{C} , \mathbf{D} are $(n \times n)$, $(n \times n)$, $(n \times n_v)$, $(n_y \times n)$ and $(n_y \times n_v)$ sized arrays, respectively.

Figure 2. Detailed Interpolation-Based ROM Methods (relevant review/survey articles are cited in each subheader).

(a) T1: POD/Snapshot-based Projection

Let $\mathcal{M} = \{\mathbf{u}(t, \mu) : 0 \leq t \leq T, \mu \in \mathcal{D}\} \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ denote the solution space of an evolution law, that is expressed in a general form similar to Equation (2.1)

$$\mathbf{E}(\mu)\dot{\mathbf{u}}(t, \mu) = f(\mathbf{u}(t, \mu), \mu), \quad (2.5)$$

where $\mathbf{E}(\mu)$ is symmetric positive definite (SPD) unless stated otherwise. Choosing sampling grids $\{t_i\}_{i=1}^{N_t} \subset [0, T]$ and $\{\mu_j\}_{j=1}^M \subset \mathcal{D}$, a *snapshot matrix* \mathbf{S} is assembled, in the form

$$\mathbf{S} = [\mathbf{u}(t_i, \mu_j)]_{i=1, \dots, N_t}^{j=1, \dots, M} \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times N}, \quad N = N_t N_\mu. \quad (2.6)$$

The singular value decomposition (SVD) $\mathbf{S} = \mathbf{U}\Sigma\mathbf{Z}^\top$ generates left singular vectors $\mathbf{U}(:, 1:r) =: \mathbf{V}$ that minimise the Frobenius-norm projection residual

$$\|\mathbf{S} - \mathbf{V}\mathbf{V}^\top\mathbf{S}\|_F \quad \text{for a prescribed energy tolerance } 0 < \varepsilon \ll 1. \quad (2.7)$$

The column-orthonormal trial basis is denoted by $\mathbf{V} \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times r}$, while the test basis is denoted by $\mathbf{W} \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times r}$. Unless a specific test basis is mentioned, a Galerkin projection is assumed with $\mathbf{W} = \mathbf{V}$.

Figure 3. Illustration of localized POD bases. The depicted points lie in the space of *reduced* models, not in the full solution space \mathcal{M} .

All matrix norms $\|\cdot\|_F$ refer to the Frobenius norm, unless otherwise specified. For each family of methods presented in the following sections, a pseudocode algorithm is presented in the **supplementary material**.

Retaining r singular values $\sigma_1, \dots, \sigma_r$ such that $\sum_{k=1}^r \sigma_k^2 / \sum_{k=1}^N \sigma_k^2 \geq 1 - \varepsilon$ yields the *trial basis* $\mathbf{V} \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times r}$. Inserting the Galerkin ansatz $\mathbf{u}(t, \mu) \approx \mathbf{V}\hat{\mathbf{u}}(t, \mu)$ into Equation (2.5) and left-multiplying by \mathbf{V}^\top produces the reduced system

$$\underbrace{\mathbf{V}^\top \mathbf{E}(\mu) \mathbf{V}}_{\mathbf{E}(\mu)} \dot{\hat{\mathbf{u}}}(t, \mu) = \underbrace{\mathbf{V}^\top f(\mathbf{V}\hat{\mathbf{u}}(t, \mu), \mu)}_{\hat{f}(\hat{\mathbf{u}}, \mu)}, \quad \forall \hat{\mathbf{u}}(t, \mu) \in \mathbb{R}^r, \quad (2.8)$$

which evolves optimally in the linear subspace $\text{range}(\mathbf{V})$.

For non-SPD matrices or strongly convective operators (i.e. operators dominated by directional transport or convection, where the state travels along distinct flow paths rather than diffusing), the normal Galerkin projection can become unstable since it minimises the residual in the typical L^2 norm which does not account for directional transport. In this case the *Petrov–Galerkin* variant replaces \mathbf{V}^\top by a test basis \mathbf{W}^\top to minimise the residual in a weighted norm [13] that reflects the physical properties of the operator.

Historical refinements illustrate the flexibility of snapshot-POD. Early parametric extensions, as illustrated in Figure 3(b) interpolated modal coefficients with cubic splines [17, 55] but were criticised for violating orthogonality and ignoring principal angles [20]. *GPOD* overcomes these issues by stacking all snapshots before the decomposition [57], whereas the alternate *sample-stacking* strategy in [54] appends new snapshots online when an error indicator exceeds a threshold. Parameter-space clustering yields *localized POD* [58], in which several compact bases coexist and must later be blended (see Figure 3(a)). Spectral variants based on Chebyshev polynomials were additionally employed for hydrodynamic stability analysis [56].

Despite such advances, a fixed linear subspace cannot fully capture highly curved regions of \mathcal{M} , forcing either a large r or reduced accuracy. Moreover, coefficient interpolation alone cannot guarantee observation of stability outside the training set. These limitations motivate subsequent families that interpolate reduced operators, and ultimately the manifold-based techniques reviewed later in this paper.

(b) T2: Transfer-Function and System-Matrix Interpolation

When the reduced basis varies with the parameter, regenerating the appropriate basis and re-projecting the full operators at every query dominates online cost. Subsequently, freezing the basis at each training point μ_i was proposed in [30]. This approach involves computing the

Figure 4. Alignment of parameter-dependent reduced operators for interpolation.

corresponding reduced operators of an LTI system ($\hat{\mathbf{A}}_i \in \mathbb{R}^{r \times r}$, $\hat{\mathbf{B}}_i \in \mathbb{R}^{r \times n_v}$, $\hat{\mathbf{C}}_i \in \mathbb{R}^{n_y \times r}$, $\hat{\mathbf{D}}_i \in \mathbb{R}^{n_y \times n_v}$, $\hat{\mathbf{E}}_i \in \mathbb{R}^{r \times r}$), and reconstructing the ROM at a new parameter μ^* by interpolating only these *small* matrices. Because each reduced order model lives in its own coordinate frame, the trial spaces must first be aligned. To this end, selecting a reference basis $\mathbf{V}_0 \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times r}$, one solves the orthogonal Procrustes problem [102]

$$\mathbf{Q}_i = \arg \min_{\mathbf{Q} \in \text{SO}(r)} \|\mathbf{V}_0 - \mathbf{V}_i \mathbf{Q}\|_F, \quad i = 1, \dots, M, \quad (2.9)$$

whose closed-form solution is $\mathbf{Q}_i = \mathbf{U}_i \mathbf{Z}_i^\top$ where $\mathbf{V}_0^\top \mathbf{V}_i = \mathbf{U}_i \mathbf{\Sigma}_i \mathbf{Z}_i^\top$ is the thin SVD. $\text{SO}(r)$ denotes the group of rotations in an r -dimensional Euclidean space. The congruence transformations $\tilde{\mathbf{A}}_i = \mathbf{Q}_i^\top \hat{\mathbf{A}}_i \mathbf{Q}_i$, $\tilde{\mathbf{B}}_i = \mathbf{Q}_i^\top \hat{\mathbf{B}}_i$, $\tilde{\mathbf{C}}_i = \hat{\mathbf{C}}_i \mathbf{Q}_i$, $\tilde{\mathbf{D}}_i = \hat{\mathbf{D}}_i$, $\tilde{\mathbf{E}}_i = \mathbf{Q}_i^\top \hat{\mathbf{E}}_i \mathbf{Q}_i$ expresses every reduced operator in the common frame \mathbf{V}_0 . Each entry then varies smoothly with μ and is interpolated component-wise, for example by cubic B-splines,

$$\tilde{\mathbf{A}}(\mu_*) = \sum_{i=0}^M \varphi_i(\mu_*) \tilde{\mathbf{A}}_i, \quad \sum_{i=0}^M \varphi_i(\mu_*) = 1, \quad (2.10)$$

and analogously for $\tilde{\mathbf{B}}$, $\tilde{\mathbf{C}}$, $\tilde{\mathbf{D}}$ and $\tilde{\mathbf{E}}$. Evaluating Equation (2.10) costs only $O(r^2)$ and is independent of the full dimension n . The procedure is schematically summarized in Figure 4.

When state snapshots are unavailable, a fully non-intrusive alternative constructs a reduced order realization directly from frequency-response data (i.e., transfer functions \mathbf{H}) via the *Loewner pencil* [103]. Given pairs (ω_j, ω_k) , the Loewner matrices $\mathbf{L}_{kj} = (\mathbf{H}_k - \mathbf{H}_j)/(\omega_k - \omega_j)$ and $\mathbf{L}_{\sigma,kj} = (\omega_k \mathbf{H}_k - \omega_j \mathbf{H}_j)/(\omega_k - \omega_j)$ yield the generalised eigenproblem $(\mathbf{L}_{\sigma,kj} - \lambda \mathbf{L}_{kj})\mathbf{v} = 0$, whose dominant modes produce $(\tilde{\mathbf{A}}_i, \tilde{\mathbf{B}}_i, \tilde{\mathbf{C}}_i)$ that interpolate the measured transfer function at μ_* . Aligning and interpolating these factors proceeds exactly as above. It is important to note that in the classic Loewner framework, the descriptor matrix \mathbf{E} is assumed invertible and its effect is absorbed into the recovered \mathbf{A} , \mathbf{B} , \mathbf{C} matrices, so it is not directly recoverable; the direct feedthrough matrix \mathbf{D} , however, is explicitly recovered from the transfer-function data.

For scalar outputs, Kriging approximates the response with Gaussian random fields and provides a local uncertainty estimate that guides adaptive sampling [64]. If the reduced matrices must remain SPD, each $\tilde{\mathbf{A}}_i$ is mapped by the matrix logarithm to the flat tangent space, interpolated, and exponentiated, thereby preserving definiteness (analogous to manifold methods, as described in Section 2(g)). This strategy may alternatively be recast on the Lie group $\text{GL}(r)$ using Bézier curves that avoid logarithmic coordinate singularities [65]. Interpolating reduced operators eliminates all online FOM cost but does not guarantee that the interpolated system will be stable or passive. Such properties require the structure-preserving machinery

revisited in the balanced-truncation family and are fully resolved only by the Grassmann-manifold construction discussed later in the review.

(c) T3: Gramian / Balanced-truncation

Balanced truncation analyses a linear, time-invariant FOM in the form

$$\dot{\mathbf{u}}(t, \mu) = \mathbf{A}(\mu) \mathbf{u}(t, \mu) + \mathbf{B}(\mu) \mathbf{x}(t), \quad \mathbf{y}(t, \mu) = \mathbf{C}(\mu) \mathbf{u}(t, \mu) \quad (2.11)$$

purely through its input–output behavior. For each fixed parameter μ , controllability and observability are quantified by the positive-definite Gramians

$$\mathbf{A}P + P\mathbf{A}^\top = -\mathbf{B}\mathbf{B}^\top, \quad \mathbf{A}^\top Q + Q\mathbf{A} = -\mathbf{C}^\top \mathbf{C}, \quad (2.12)$$

obtained from the Lyapunov equations [104]. A similarity transformation $\mathbf{T}_{BT}(\mu)$ that satisfies $\mathbf{T}_{BT}P\mathbf{T}_{BT}^\top = \mathbf{T}_{BT}^{-\top}Q\mathbf{T}_{BT}^{-1} = \mathbf{\Sigma}(\mu)$ places the system in a *balanced* form where the diagonal matrix $\mathbf{\Sigma}(\mu) = \text{diag}(\sigma_1(\mu), \dots, \sigma_n(\mu))$ contains the Hankel singular values. Discarding the states associated with $\sigma_{r+1}, \dots, \sigma_n$ produces a reduced order model whose transfer function $\hat{\mathbf{H}}(s, \mu)$ satisfies the Moore error bound

$$\|\mathbf{H}(\cdot, \mu) - \hat{\mathbf{H}}(\cdot, \mu)\|_{\mathcal{H}_\infty} \leq 2 \sum_{k=r+1}^n \sigma_k(\mu), \quad (2.13)$$

where $\mathbf{H}(s, \mu) = \mathbf{C}(\mu)(s\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{A}(\mu))^{-1}\mathbf{B}(\mu) + \mathbf{D}(\mu)$ is the full-order transfer function. For large-scale models, direct Schur methods [47] are infeasible and one instead approximates the Gramians by Cholesky inspired low-rank factors $P \approx \mathbf{L}_c\mathbf{L}_c^\top$ and $Q \approx \mathbf{L}_o\mathbf{L}_o^\top$. The alternating-direction implicit (ADI) iteration computes \mathbf{L}_c via the shift sequence $\{\gamma_j\}$

$$(\mathbf{A} + \gamma_j\mathbf{I})\mathbf{L}_{c,j} = -\mathbf{B}\mathbf{B}^\top - (\mathbf{A} - \bar{\gamma}_j\mathbf{I}) \sum_{k < j} \mathbf{L}_{c,k}\mathbf{L}_{c,k}^\top, \quad j = 1, \dots, \ell, \quad (2.14)$$

with only $\ell \approx 10 - 50$ columns required because the spectrum of P decays rapidly [105]. Weighted variants replace Equation (2.12) by generalised Lyapunov equations that embed a frequency-shaping filter $W(s)$, thereby emphasising accuracy in prescribed bands.

Modern extensions sidestep Lyapunov solves altogether. By writing $P = \mathbf{L}_c\mathbf{L}_c^\top$, one solves a Riemannian optimisation problem by minimizing the residual $\|\mathbf{A}\mathbf{L}_c\mathbf{L}_c^\top + \mathbf{L}_c\mathbf{L}_c^\top\mathbf{A}^\top + \mathbf{B}\mathbf{B}^\top\|_F^2$ directly on the fixed-rank manifold, using conjugate gradients with rank-preserving properties [71]. Because each new parameter μ demands a fresh Lyapunov solve, computational cost is controlled by *interpolating* the low-rank factors. Every factor $\mathbf{L}_c(\mu_i) \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times \ell}$ spans an ℓ -dimensional subspace, which is a point on the Grassmann manifold $G(n, \ell)$. Mapping those points to the tangent space at a reference subspace and interpolating the resulting tangent vectors, as detailed in the algorithms section of the *supplementary material*, preserves both rank and smoothness across parameters while avoiding repeated Lyapunov solves. After retraction back to $G(n, \ell)$, the balanced coordinates are recomputed and truncated, thereby recovering the error guarantee Equation (2.13) empirically. A formal proof for the interpolated case remains an open challenge, which partly explains why Gramian-based techniques are rarer in industrial black-box pipelines than the fully non-intrusive families reviewed next. It should be noted that this methodological extension draws extensively on the manifold-interpolation framework presented later in Section 2(g).

(d) T4: Krylov / Interpolatory (Moment-Matching)

Krylov-based reduction constructs a ROM whose transfer function $\mathbf{H}(s, \mu) = \mathbf{C}(\mu)(s\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{A}(\mu))^{-1}\mathbf{B}(\mu) + \mathbf{D}(\mu)$ matches a prescribed number of Taylor coefficients (moments) of the

Figure 5. Interpolatory Moment matching through rational Krylov subspaces: (a) Reduced Order Model approximates $r_l = 2$ moments of the Full Order Transfer Function (magnitude and slope), and (b) an illustration of the IRKA framework.

full-order model about selected *expansion points* $s = s_\ell$. Writing

$$\mathbf{H}(s, \mu) = \sum_{k \geq 0} (s - s_\ell)^k \mathbf{C}(\mu) (\mathbf{A}(\mu) - s_\ell \mathbf{I})^{-k-1} \mathbf{B}(\mu), \quad (2.15)$$

reveals that the first r_ℓ moments are spanned by

$$\mathcal{K}_{r_\ell}(\mathbf{A}(\mu) - s_\ell \mathbf{I}, \mathbf{B}(\mu)) = \text{span}\{ (\mathbf{A}(\mu) - s_\ell \mathbf{I})^{-k} \mathbf{B}(\mu) : 0 \leq k \leq r_\ell - 1 \}. \quad (2.16)$$

A block-Arnoldi or Lanczos recurrence orthonormalises the columns of $(\mathbf{A} - s_\ell \mathbf{I})^{-1} \mathbf{B}$, $(\mathbf{A} - s_\ell \mathbf{I})^{-2} \mathbf{B}$, \dots , to form the trial basis \mathbf{V} , while a bi-orthogonal recurrence with output directions $\mathbf{C}(\mu)^\top$ yields the test basis \mathbf{W} . Projection $\hat{\mathbf{A}} = \mathbf{W}^\top \mathbf{A}(\mu) \mathbf{V}$, $\hat{\mathbf{B}} = \mathbf{W}^\top \mathbf{B}(\mu)$, $\hat{\mathbf{C}} = \mathbf{C}(\mu) \mathbf{V}$ then enforces exact moment matching for orders up to r_ℓ at s_ℓ .

The *Iterative Rational Krylov Algorithm* (IRKA) [106] refines the shifts s_ℓ and the associated tangential directions by reflecting the current reduced-order poles, $s_\ell \leftarrow -\hat{\lambda}_\ell$, until the first-order \mathcal{H}_2 -optimality conditions are satisfied. Extensions to bilinear and quadratic-bilinear systems replace each Sylvester solution with coupled generalized Lyapunov equations (the BIRKA framework [47]); second-order mechanical models employ structure-preserving Lanczos recurrences that honour the mass-stiffness partitioning.

Parametric moment-matching (multivariate Padé) simultaneously matches frequency and parameter derivatives by augmenting the Krylov space with blocks of the form $(\mathbf{A} - s_\ell \mathbf{I})^{-k} \partial_{\mu_j}^\beta \mathbf{B}$, but the resulting basis dimension grows combinatorially in the number of parameters and derivative orders. This combinatorial explosion motivates hybrid schemes such as sampling-based RB or interpolation of reduced operator. This avoids constructing prohibitively large Krylov spaces.

Moment-matching origins trace back to Padé-type rational interpolation in control theory [69], with early model-reduction algorithms based on Lanczos recurrences [78]. While IRKA brought \mathcal{H}_2 -optimality to first-order systems [107], its direct extension to large-scale, high-parameter, problems remains challenging. The lack of a priori error bounds for general nonlinear or time-varying systems, and the growth of basis size with each new shift or parameter direction, limit its applicability to moderate-dimensional parameter studies. Recent work investigates adaptive shift selection driven by local error surrogates and tangent-space interpolation of Krylov subspaces [108], but the development of a fully scalable, guaranteed-accuracy parametric IRKA is still an open problem.

(e) T5: Parameter-sampling and Reduced-basis

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Figure 6. Adaptive sampling on a Smolyak sparse grid; basis vectors are added only where the current error bound is large [109].

The reduced-basis (RB) paradigm dispenses with a fixed tensor grid and instead grows the trial space $\mathbf{V} \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times r}$ adaptively, guided by a certified residual bound. The method applies to many forms of discretised operator Partial Differential Equations (PDE). For consistency purposes, we assume the LTI state space model of Equation (2.3). A reduced-order approximation is obtained by projecting the FOM onto a trial basis $\mathbf{V} \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times r}$ with $r \ll n$

$$\mathbf{u}(t, \mu) \approx \mathbf{V} \hat{\mathbf{u}}(t, \mu), \quad \hat{\mathbf{u}}(t, \mu) \in \mathbb{R}^r. \quad (2.17)$$

The family of methods is agnostic to the way used to derive the trial basis \mathbf{V} . This can be derived using any projection type reduced modeling technique on the FOM, like for example POD, Balanced Truncation, Krylov subspaces etc. Applying a Galerkin projection (or Petrov - Galerkin with test basis \mathbf{W}^T) leads to the reduced system

$$\hat{\mathbf{E}}(\mu) \dot{\hat{\mathbf{u}}}(t, \mu) = \hat{\mathbf{A}}(\mu) \hat{\mathbf{u}}(t, \mu) + \hat{\mathbf{B}}(\mu) \mathbf{v}_{in}(t), \quad (2.18)$$

$$\hat{\mathbf{y}}(t, \mu) = \hat{\mathbf{C}}(\mu) \hat{\mathbf{u}}(t, \mu) + \mathbf{D}(\mu) \mathbf{v}_{in}(t), \quad (2.19)$$

where $\hat{\mathbf{E}}(\mu) = \mathbf{W}^T \mathbf{E}(\mu) \mathbf{V}$, $\hat{\mathbf{A}}(\mu) = \mathbf{W}^T \mathbf{A}(\mu) \mathbf{V}$, $\hat{\mathbf{B}}(\mu) = \mathbf{W}^T \mathbf{B}(\mu)$ and $\hat{\mathbf{C}}(\mu) = \mathbf{C}(\mu) \mathbf{V}$. Assuming an affine decomposition

$$\mathbf{E}(\mu) = \sum_{q=1}^{Q_E} \theta_E^{(q)}(\mu) \mathbf{E}_q, \quad \mathbf{A}(\mu) = \sum_{q=1}^{Q_A} \theta_A^{(q)}(\mu) \mathbf{A}_q, \quad \mathbf{B}(\mu) = \sum_{q=1}^{Q_B} \theta_B^{(q)}(\mu) \mathbf{B}_q, \quad (2.20)$$

the reduced matrices $\hat{\mathbf{E}}_q = \mathbf{W}^T \mathbf{E}_q \mathbf{V}$, $\hat{\mathbf{A}}_q = \mathbf{W}^T \mathbf{A}_q \mathbf{V}$ and $\hat{\mathbf{B}}_q = \mathbf{W}^T \mathbf{B}_q$ are pre-assembled offline. Evaluating all parameters in the training set,

$$\hat{\mathbf{E}}(\mu^*) = \sum_{q=1}^{Q_E} \theta_E^{(q)}(\mu^*) \hat{\mathbf{E}}_q, \quad \hat{\mathbf{A}}(\mu^*) = \sum_{q=1}^{Q_A} \theta_A^{(q)}(\mu^*) \hat{\mathbf{A}}_q, \quad \hat{\mathbf{B}}(\mu^*) = \sum_{q=1}^{Q_B} \theta_B^{(q)}(\mu^*) \hat{\mathbf{B}}_q, \quad (2.21)$$

then costs $O(r^2)$, independent of the full dimension n .

Given the reduced solution $\hat{\mathbf{u}}(\mu^*)$ computed by solving the reduced-order system, the Galerkin residual can be computed as

$$\mathbf{r}(\mu^*) = \mathbf{E}(\mu^*) \mathbf{V} \dot{\hat{\mathbf{u}}}(\mu^*) - \mathbf{A}(\mu^*) \mathbf{V} \hat{\mathbf{u}}(\mu^*) - \mathbf{B}(\mu^*) \mathbf{v}_{in}(t). \quad (2.22)$$

The residual is evaluated in a dual norm that admits an efficient upper bound $\Delta(\mu^*)$ thanks to the affine decomposition [110]. A greedy loop selects the parameter of the training set with the highest residual: $\mu^* = \arg \max_{\mu \in \mathcal{P}_{\text{train}}} \Delta(\mu)$, adds the corresponding high-fidelity snapshot to the basis, and repeats until $\max_{\mu \in \mathcal{P}_{\text{train}}} \Delta(\mu) \leq \varepsilon_{\text{RB}}$, where $\mathcal{P}_{\text{train}}$ and ε_{RB} denote training parameter sets and convergence tolerances, respectively.

When the operator is non-affine or nonlinear as in Equation (2.1), the Empirical Interpolation Method (EIM) and its discrete variant (DEIM) introduce a collateral basis \mathbf{U}_m and index set P such that

$$f(\mathbf{u}, \mu) \approx \mathbf{U}_m (\mathbf{P}^\top \mathbf{U}_m)^{-1} \mathbf{P}^\top f(\mathbf{u}, \mu), \quad m \ll n, \quad (2.23)$$

so that only m entries of the nonlinear term are evaluated online. Smolyak sparse grids further compress the training set to a lattice whose size grows only polynomially with the parametric dimension while preserving exactness up to a chosen degree [111]. For highly variable dynamics one may even partition the parameter space in subregions, each with its own local reduced basis.

RB provides rigorous error certification but remains intrusive: assembling the residual and its dual norm requires access to system matrices that are often unavailable in commercial solvers (element level stiffness and mass matrices in a Finite Element Analysis (FEA) context) [112]. Moreover, the trial space remains a single linear subspace of \mathbb{R}^n . As a result, strongly curved solution manifolds may require a large reduced dimension r , motivating the development of manifold approaches discussed later.

(f) T6: Structure-preserving, Passive and Second-order Techniques

Many physical models carry invariants, e.g., symplectic form, passivity, or matrix positive-definiteness, that must remain unchanged during reduction and interpolation. In the case of the second-order mechanical system we have

$$\mathbf{M}(\mu) \ddot{\mathbf{q}} + \mathbf{K}(\mu) \mathbf{q} = \mathbf{f}(t, \mu), \quad (2.24)$$

where M, K are the mass and stiffness, parameter depending, matrices respectively, and \mathbf{f} is a loading vector. Selecting the first r eigenpairs $\mathbf{K}\mathbf{x}_j = \lambda_j \mathbf{M}\mathbf{x}_j$ and mass-orthonormalising them yields the displacement basis $\mathbf{V}^x(\mu) \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times r}$ with $\mathbf{V}^{x\top} \mathbf{M} \mathbf{V}^x = \mathbb{I}$. Defining the velocity basis $\mathbf{V}^v(\mu) = \mathbf{M}^{-1} \mathbf{K} \mathbf{V}^x \mathbf{\Lambda}(\mu)^{-1/2}$ with $\mathbf{\Lambda} = \mathbf{V}^{x\top} \mathbf{K} \mathbf{V}^x$ and stacking $\mathbf{T}_2 = [\mathbf{V}^x \ \mathbf{V}^v]$ converts the dynamics to a reduced Hamiltonian pair $(\hat{\mathbf{J}}, \hat{\mathbf{G}})$ that conserves the hamiltonian function (in this case, energy) $H(\hat{\mathbf{z}}) = \frac{1}{2} \hat{\mathbf{z}}^\top \hat{\mathbf{G}} \hat{\mathbf{z}}$. The procedure as summarised in the relevant Algorithm of the *supplementary material* guarantees structure preservation at every training parameter μ_i ; interpolation of $(\hat{\mathbf{J}}, \hat{\mathbf{G}})$ then extends these guarantees to unseen parameters at negligible cost.

For input–output systems, coprime factorisation expresses the transfer function as: $\mathbf{H}(s) = \mathbf{N}(s) \mathbf{D}^{-1}(s)$ with stable factors [113]. Interpolating \mathbf{N} and \mathbf{D} separately maintains passivity for all μ [51]. Spectral-zero interpolation further enforces that the ROM inherits the transmission zeros of the full model, ensuring loss-free behaviour [114]. When reduced matrices must remain symmetric positive-definite, each sample is mapped via the matrix logarithm [53], interpolated in the Euclidean space of symmetric matrices, and exponentiated, thereby prohibiting negative eigenvalues [115]. The system described in Equation (2.24) does not include damping in its formulation so that a strict Hamiltonian formulation applies. In the more general case, damping can be considered by including a dissipative term in the Hamiltonian function, e.g. using a port-Hamiltonian or dissipative Hamiltonian framework, which preserves energy decay and other structural properties [116]. These guarantees incur offline cost: computing Hamiltonian eigenbases, matrix logarithms, or coprime factors must be repeated at every training point, and fine frequency grids may be necessary. The quest for cheaper yet structure-aware interpolation of the *subspaces themselves* motivates the manifold techniques collected in Family T7.

(g) T7: Manifold-based Interpolation of Reduced Bases

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Figure 7. Interpolation of reduced subspaces on the Grassmann manifold. Support subspaces $[\mathbf{V}_j]$ are mapped via the logarithm to the common tangent space at the reference $[\mathbf{V}_1]$, blended by inverse-distance weights, and returned through the exponential map to furnish the query basis $[\mathbf{V}_*]$.

The Grassmann manifold $G(n, r)$, as illustrated in Figure 7, is a collection of all r -planes spanned by column-orthonormal bases $\mathbf{V} \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times r}$ and provides a natural stage for their interpolation. Each support parameter μ_j is associated with a reduced bases $[\mathbf{V}_j] \in G(n, r)$. Choosing a reference $[\mathbf{V}_0]$, every other subspace is expressed in the tangent space $T_{[\mathbf{V}_0]}G$ through

$$\mathbf{X}_i = \log_{[\mathbf{V}_0]}([\mathbf{V}_j]) = \mathbf{U}_j \arctan(\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_j) \mathbf{Z}_j^T, \quad (\mathbf{U}_j \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_j \mathbf{Z}_j^T) = \text{svd}[(\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{V}_0 \mathbf{V}_0^T) \mathbf{V}_j (\mathbf{V}_0^T \mathbf{V}_j)^{-1}]. \quad (2.25)$$

Inverse-distance weights of order q blend these tangent vectors as

$$\mathbf{T}(\boldsymbol{\mu}) = \sum_j \frac{\|\boldsymbol{\mu} - \boldsymbol{\mu}_j\|^{-q}}{\sum_k \|\boldsymbol{\mu} - \boldsymbol{\mu}_k\|^{-q}} \log_{[\mathbf{V}_0]}([\mathbf{V}_j]), \quad (2.26)$$

and the exponential map supplies the interpolated basis

$$\mathbf{V}(\boldsymbol{\mu}_*) = \mathbf{V}_1 \mathbf{Z} \cos \boldsymbol{\Theta} + \mathbf{U} \sin \boldsymbol{\Theta}, \quad (\mathbf{U} \boldsymbol{\Theta} \mathbf{Z}^T) = \text{svd}(\mathbf{T}(\boldsymbol{\mu})). \quad (2.27)$$

Only two thin SVDs of size $n \times r$ are required per query. This is negligible compared with any high-fidelity solve. The reference-free inverse-distance variants [117, 118] are recovered as special cases.

Strong parameter dependence often forces several local POD spaces. Partitioning the domain $\mathcal{D} = \bigcup_k \mathcal{D}_k$ and forming local bases \mathbf{V}_k from snapshots restricted to \mathcal{D}_k keeps each rank small [119, 120]. A discontinuous switch to \mathbf{V}_k whenever $\boldsymbol{\mu} \in \mathcal{D}_k$ is avoided by the pre-average $\tilde{\mathbf{V}}(\boldsymbol{\mu}) = \sum_k w_k(\boldsymbol{\mu}) \mathbf{V}_k$, where the smooth weights originate from k -means or fuzzy clustering [121–125]. Because $\tilde{\mathbf{V}}$ is not orthonormal, it is projected back to $G(n, r)$ with the logarithm–exponential pair [117]. A related trajectory-pieceswise linear approach approximates the dynamics by linear models that are themselves interpolated [126–128].

When the snapshot matrices have different numerical ranks, their associated column spaces no longer reside on the same Grassmann manifold but on Schubert varieties. These are nested subsets of the Grassmannian corresponding to subspaces of different dimensions. To enable interpolation,

these subspaces must first be brought to a common dimensional setting. This can be done either by truncating all bases to the smallest shared rank or by lifting them to the largest rank through appropriate zero-padding or basis extension. Figure 8 illustrates this process using the truncation strategy, which, as shown in [129], generally provides better accuracy–cost trade-offs for most practical applications.

Figure 8. Interpolation across unequal ranks. Subspaces of dimension $r_A < r_B$ inhabit distinct Schubert varieties (blue and green). Truncation to $G(n, r_A)$ yields a well-defined geodesic construction [129].

Grassmann interpolation automatically preserves the orthogonality of the basis and decouples basis adaptation from the evaluation of system operators. However, properties such as stability, passivity, and symplectic structure are not preserved inherently. These must be re-introduced using the techniques provided by *T6: Structure-preserving, Passive and Second-order Techniques*. Its minimal online cost has nevertheless rendered it integral to the architecture of digital-twin frameworks and multi-fidelity pipelines in computational mechanics and flow control [130, 131]. A key reason is that many engineering design problems involve extremely large parameter spaces where repeated high-fidelity evaluations are infeasible. Composite-laminate design is a prime example: immense ply-angle design spaces render global reductions impractical, and local manifolds combined with inverse-distance blending or barycentric schemes have proved effective [11, 132–134]. Recent work couples these interpolants with non-uniform B-spline hypersurfaces to capture multi-scale interactions [10, 135, 136]. Despite these advances, interpolation across subspaces of varying dimension remains sparsely studied. This capability is essential for thick-ply configurations, where inter-laminar stresses play a dominant role. However, it is currently absent from laminate damage-optimisation workflows [137–139]. Developing rank-adaptive strategies that exploit physics-informed sampling grids [140] and preserve critical interface phenomena is therefore an open problem for future reduced-order modeling research.

Table 3: Advantages and limitations of each interpolation-based ROM family.

	Key strengths	Principal drawbacks
T1:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Energy-optimal SVD basis. Galerkin projection preserves structure. Low computational cost. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Breaks under non-SPD state matrices. Fixed subspace; poor on curved manifolds. Basis size grows with parameter dimension. Naïve interpolation breaks orthonormality.
T2:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fully non-intrusive online use. $\mathcal{O}(r^2)$ cost only. Compatible with Loewner and Gaussian-process surrogates. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Requires congruence alignment. No guaranteed stability or passivity. Accuracy degrades if local bases differ significantly.

continued on next page

(Table 3 continued)

	Key strengths	Principal drawbacks
T3:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A-priori $\mathcal{H}_2/\mathcal{H}_\infty$ error bounds. • Ensures stability and norm preservation. • Low-rank ADI scales efficiently for large n. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Requires a Lyapunov solve per parameter sample. • Bounds become invalid under naive interpolation. • Applicable only to LTI systems.
T4:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Exact moment matching at expansion points. • IRKA yields near-optimal \mathcal{H}_2 approximations. • Tangential interpolation for MIMO systems. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Basis size grows with number of shifts. • No inherent stability or passivity guarantee. • Padé-type extension scales poorly in high dimensions. • Only applicable to LTI systems.
T5:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Certified error bounds via greedy sampling. • Online cost independent of full dimension n. • Integrates with DEIM/ECSW hyper-reduction. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Intrusive assembly of residuals and coercivity constants. • Rarely exact affine decomposition; EIM may inflate basis size. • Fixed linear subspace inefficient for strongly curved manifolds.
T6:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Preserves SPD, passivity, and symplectic structure. • Guaranteed long-term stability. • Compatible with component-mode and coprime-factor methods. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Computing matrix logarithms or Hamiltonian bases is costly. • Structural constraints reduce interpolation flexibility. • Online evaluation still expensive without further reduction.
T7:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Direct interpolation on $G(n, r)$ or $S(n, r)$. • Coordinate-free invariance of interpolant. • Only two thin SVDs required per query. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No inherent enforcement of stability or symmetry. • Requires operator projections for dynamic systems. • SVD cost may matter in strict real-time applications.

Table 3 provides a concise comparison of the principal techniques, highlighting their respective advantages and limitations. At the heart of contemporary methods lies the Grassmann manifold $G(n, r)$, which guarantees that any interpolated basis remains a valid r -dimensional subspace of \mathbb{R}^n . Key geometric constructs, i.e., geodesics, tangent spaces and exponential/logarithmic maps, equip us with the means to navigate these manifolds. By combining these mathematical frameworks, interpolation-based ROMs achieve continuous, stable and physically consistent approximations across the full parameter domain.

3. CONSTRUCTION & DEPLOYMENT

(a) Unified Workflow & Complexity Landscape

The seven families T1–7 analysed in Section 2 define the *ingredients* of interpolation-based model reduction; the present section distills those ingredients into a generic six-stage workflow the details of which apply naturally to any chosen family.

- (i) **Snapshot acquisition.** A design-of-experiments selects parameter samples $\{\boldsymbol{\mu}_i\}_{i=1}^M \subset \mathcal{D}$. For each $\boldsymbol{\mu}_i$, the FOM is solved; in unsteady problems, this is done at discrete times $\{t_k\}_{k=1}^{N_t} \subset [0, T]$. The resulting solutions are assembled into the snapshot matrix $\mathbf{S} = [\mathbf{u}(t_k, \boldsymbol{\mu}_i)]_{k,i} \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times N}$. This stage dominates the offline computational cost.
- (ii) **Basis generation.** In *global POD*, a single thin SVD $\mathbf{S} = \mathbf{U}\boldsymbol{\Sigma}\mathbf{Z}^\top$ is performed, and the first r left singular vectors $\mathbf{V} = \mathbf{U}(:, 1:r)$ are retained to capture a user predefined accuracy of the original snapshot. The amount of left singular vectors to be kept is typically defined with an error term ε and the amount of vectors kept is such that the reduced order system maintains $(1 - \varepsilon)$ accuracy of the FOM. In *local POD*, the snapshot matrix is partitioned by parameter binning or clustering, and separate local bases $\mathbf{V}(\boldsymbol{\mu}_i)$ are computed. Ranks may differ across regions and are equalized through truncation or zero-padding followed by re-orthonormalization.
- (iii) **Coordinate homogenisation.** Interpolation requires a shared reference frame. For *subspace-based* strategies, a reference basis \mathbf{V}_0 is selected, and each support subspace is mapped to the tangent space $T_{[\mathbf{V}_0]}G(n, r)$ via the Grassmann logarithm, yielding tangent vectors \mathbf{X}_i . For *reduced-matrix* approaches, local bases are aligned to \mathbf{V}_0 using the orthogonal Procrustes rotation $\mathbf{Q}_i = \arg \min_{\mathbf{Q} \in \text{SO}(r)} \|\mathbf{V}_0 - \mathbf{V}(\boldsymbol{\mu}_i)\mathbf{Q}\|_F$, and the reduced operators are rotated accordingly.
- (iv) **Offline interpolation model.**

Figure 9. End-to-end workflow for an interpolation-based reduced-order model. Blue parallelograms indicate data objects passed between phases, using the common notation of Section 2.

- a. In subspace interpolation, the map $I_M : \mathcal{D} \rightarrow T_{[\mathbf{V}_0]}G(n, r)$ constructed using, for example, radial basis functions, blends the tangent vectors, and the exponential map retrieves the interpolated basis as $\mathbf{V}(\boldsymbol{\mu}) = \exp_{[\mathbf{V}_0]}(I_M(\boldsymbol{\mu}))$.
 - b. In reduced-matrix interpolation, the aligned reduced operators $\tilde{\mathbf{A}}_i, \tilde{\mathbf{B}}_i, \tilde{\mathbf{C}}_i, \tilde{\mathbf{D}}_i$ are interpolated entry-wise. To preserve properties like symmetry or passivity, the matrices are first mapped to the tangent space of $\text{SPD}(r)$ via the matrix logarithm, interpolated, and then exponentiated.
- (v) **Online query and ROM assembly.** Given a new parameter query $\boldsymbol{\mu}_*$, the interpolant is evaluated. In subspace variants, the interpolated basis $\mathbf{V}(\boldsymbol{\mu}_*)$ is constructed and used to project the full operators, e.g., $\hat{\mathbf{A}}(\boldsymbol{\mu}_*) = \mathbf{V}^\top \mathbf{A}(\boldsymbol{\mu}_*) \mathbf{V}$. In reduced-matrix variants, the interpolated operators $\tilde{\mathbf{A}}(\boldsymbol{\mu}_*), \dots, \tilde{\mathbf{D}}(\boldsymbol{\mu}_*)$ are used directly, without dependence on the high-dimensional space. The reduced system of size r is then assembled and can be used in place of the FOM for time integration or other form of handling depending on the case.
- (vi) **Post-processing and error control.** Desired engineering outputs are computed from the reduced solution. If certification is required, a residual-based error estimator or cross-validation error is evaluated. If the estimated error exceeds a user-defined tolerance, the model is adaptively enriched: a new snapshot is added to \mathbf{S} , the basis and interpolant are updated, and the process resumes.

Table 4: Leading-order floating-point costs per phase of the interpolation-based ROM workflow.

Task	Operation	Complexity & Remarks
Offline		
FOM solves	M high-fidelity simulations at $\boldsymbol{\mu}_i$	$\mathcal{O}(M \cdot \text{cost}(\text{FOM}))$; dominant expense, fully parallelisable
Global POD	thin-SVD of $n \times (Mk)$ snapshot matrix	$\mathcal{O}(Mkn^2)$ or $\mathcal{O}(Mknr)$ (randomised); single decomposition, $r \ll n$
Local POD	M thin-SVDs of $n \times k$ blocks	$\sum_{i=1}^M \mathcal{O}(knr_i)$; efficient when dynamics vary regionally

(continued on next page)

(Table 4 continued)

Task	Operation	Complexity & Remarks
Grassmann log	Map each $\mathbf{V}_r(\mu_i)$ to $T_{[\mathbf{V}_0]}G(n, r)$	$\mathcal{O}((M-1)nr^2)$; two thin SVDs per basis
Interpolant build	Fit RBF/spline/Kriging weights	$\mathcal{O}(M^2)$ – $\mathcal{O}(M^3)$; solve dense system for coefficients
Online		
Basis exp. map	Recover $\mathbf{V}_r(\mu^*)$ from tangent vector	$\mathcal{O}(nr^2)$; one thin SVD of $n \times r$
Full projection	Assemble $\hat{\mathbf{A}} = \mathbf{V}_r^\top \mathbf{A}(\mu^*) \mathbf{V}_r$	$\mathcal{O}(nr^2)$; semi-intrusive mode only
Operator interp.	Evaluate $\hat{\mathbf{A}}(\mu^*), \dots, \hat{\mathbf{D}}(\mu^*)$	$\mathcal{O}(r^2)$; fully non-intrusive, no n -dependence
Hyper-reduced RHS	DEIM evaluation of nonlinear term	$\mathcal{O}(m)$; $m \ll n$, optional acceleration
Solve reduced sys.	Linear/nonlinear solve of size r	$\mathcal{O}(r^3)$; negligible for $r \lesssim 200$
Optional		
Adaptive re-base	Incremental SVD + Grassmann update	$\mathcal{O}(nr)$ – $\mathcal{O}(nr^2)$; triggered if error $> \varepsilon$
Error estimator	Dual residual or cross-validation test	$\mathcal{O}(nr)$ or $\mathcal{O}(r^2)$; certification or drives enrichment

Table 4 displays the leading-order floating-point costs for each stage. Offline expense is dominated by M high-fidelity solutions and, for global POD by an SVD of size $n \times Mk$, where k denotes the number of stored time-steps per parameter. Local POD replaces this with M smaller SVDs. Grassmann logarithms and exponentials scale as $\mathcal{O}(nr^2)$ and involve only thin SVDs, negligible once r is below a few hundred. Online cost is either $\mathcal{O}(nr^2)$ when a fresh projection is required (semi-intrusive), or $\mathcal{O}(r^2)$ when interpolated operators are used (fully non-intrusive). Hyper-reduction (discussed as a methodological extension in ??) further reduces nonlinear evaluations to $\mathcal{O}(m)$ with $m \ll n$.

(b) Method-Picker: Selecting the Appropriate Interpolation Family

Table 5: Constraint-to-Method mapping for interpolation-based ROMs:
(\checkmark = well-suited, \circ = partially supported, \times = not recommended.)

Model Requirement	T1	T2	T3	T4	T5	T6	T7
Intrusive formulation (system matrices) available	\checkmark	\circ	\checkmark	\checkmark	\checkmark	\checkmark	\circ
Fully non-intrusive (black-box / data-driven)	\circ	\checkmark	\times	\circ	\circ	\circ	\checkmark
Preservation of passivity / stability required	\circ	\times	\checkmark	\circ	\circ	\checkmark	\circ
Geometry morphing or mesh movement	\circ	\circ	\circ	\circ	\circ	\circ	\checkmark
Nonlinear or time-varying right-hand sides	\circ	\times	\times	\circ	\checkmark	\circ	\checkmark
Parametric dependence highly non-affine	\circ	\checkmark	\circ	\circ	\checkmark	\circ	\checkmark
Strict real-time / control-loop deadline	\checkmark	\checkmark	\circ	\circ	\circ	\circ	\circ
High accuracy with certified error bounds	\circ	\circ	\checkmark	\checkmark	\checkmark	\circ	\circ
Structure-preserving (SPD / symplectic)	\circ	\circ	\checkmark	\circ	\circ	\checkmark	\circ
Basis adaptation / incremental update needed	\circ	\circ	\circ	\circ	\checkmark	\circ	\checkmark
Suitable for multi-fidelity or surrogate coupling	\circ	\checkmark	\circ	\circ	\checkmark	\circ	\checkmark

Practical usage of these techniques ultimately depends on the constraints of the underlying problem. As summarized in Table 3, each interpolation family favors a different levels of model intrusiveness, structural preservation, or parametric flexibility. To assist practitioners in this selection, Table 5 presents a concise constraint-to-method mapping that identifies which families are best suited for a given modeling requirement.

4. METHODOLOGICAL VARIATIONS & EXTENSIONS

While Section 2 has laid out the seven fundamental interpolation ROM paradigms, practical applications frequently demand further refinements to address computational constraints, data scarcity and noticeable geometric and structural variations. In this section, a sequence of such

extensions E1-E5 are outlined. A *detailed overview* of the proposed methods along with how they build upon T1-7 can be found in the *supplementary material* of the paper.

Figure 10. (a) E1: Comparison of classical POD (left) and hierarchical POD (right), (b) E2: Multi-fidelity model reduction with adaptive sampling: (i) low-fidelity (LF) and high-fidelity (HF) discretizations of the same geometry; (ii) surrogate fit comparisons, (c) E3: Craig–Bampton (component-mode) condensation of a bolted beam assembly. Each substructure Ω_α is discretised independently, its interior fixed-interface modes \mathbf{V}_α^i (blue) are retained, and its static constraint modes \mathbf{C}_α enforce compatibility along the purple interface mesh. Adapted from [141], (d) E4: Radial–basis–function morphing of an aircraft wing surface.

a) E1 *Hierarchical and Locally Refined POD:*

While classical POD (see Section 2(a)) uses a single SVD of the snapshot matrix \mathbf{S} to produce a global basis; hierarchical POD (HPOD) [142–144] first decomposes the parametric domain $\mathcal{D} = \bigcup \mathcal{D}_k$ as depicted in Figure 10(a) and performs an SVD for each part

$$\mathbf{S}_k = \mathbf{U}_k \Sigma_k \mathbf{Z}_k, \quad \mathbf{V}_k = \mathbf{U}_k(:, 1:r_k). \quad (4.1)$$

HPOD keeps the energy-optimal property of POD inside each part while keeping the dimension small in regions where the solution changes little. Its main weakness is that a mode which is important only in a later level can be lost during the earlier SVDs unless the indicator η_k is chosen with care.

b) E2 *Multi-Fidelity Reduction with Adaptive Sampling:*

Assume a fast but rough model \mathcal{F}_L (*L-low fidelity*) that produces the state vectors $\mathbf{u}^L(t, \mu)$ and a slow but accurate model \mathcal{F}_H (*H-high fidelity*) that produces the state vectors $\mathbf{u}^H(t, \mu)$ for the same physical problem. In a two-level reduced model, often also called a Response Surface Method, then approximates the high fidelity state as

$$\mathbf{u}^H(t, \mu) \approx \underbrace{\Pi_{L \rightarrow H}(\mathbf{V}_L \hat{\mathbf{u}}^L(t, \mu))}_{\text{LF prediction lifted to HF space}} + \underbrace{\mathbf{V}_\delta \hat{\mathbf{u}}^\delta(t, \mu)}_{\text{HF correction}} \quad (4.2)$$

where \mathbf{V}_L is obtained from many low-fidelity (LF) snapshots, $\Pi_{L \rightarrow H}$ is a lift operator, and \mathbf{V}_δ is obtained from a small number of high-fidelity (HF) corrections $\delta(\mu_j^H)$ [145, 146]. Its accuracy is limited by how well \mathcal{F}_L represents the true physics in parameter values where no HF data have yet been taken. This is illustrated in Figure 10(b).

c) **E3 Component-Mode Synthesis Sub-structuring and Matrix Interpolation:**

The Craig-Bampton approach, or Component-mode synthesis (CMS) with sub-structuring, divides a complex structure into subdomains $\{S_\alpha\}$ as shown in Figure 10(c) and condenses each part before global coupling [147]. Because substructures are handled independently, libraries of parametric components accelerate studies of damaged assemblies or modular designs [148, 149]. This approach can be combined with the Schubert-variety lifting strategy of Family T7 to accommodate rank changes without sacrificing continuity.

d) **E4 Shape Maps and Mesh Morphing:**

Geometry-dependent problems demand that both the governing operators and the trial space evolve with the shape. Let Ω_0 be a reference finite-element mesh and let $\Psi(\mathbf{x}_0, \mu) : \Omega_0 \rightarrow \Omega(\mu)$ map every reference node \mathbf{x}_0 to its deformed position \mathbf{x} for the parameter value μ , as depicted in Figure 10(d) [150]. Given a reference POD basis $\mathbf{V}^0 = [\mathbf{v}_1^0, \dots, \mathbf{v}_r^0]$ on Ω_0 , the transported field

$$\mathbf{v}_j(\mathbf{x}, \mu) = \mathbf{v}_j^0(\Psi^{-1}(\mathbf{x}, \mu)), \quad j = 1, \dots, r, \quad (4.3)$$

is well defined on the deformed mesh $\Omega(\mu)$ [151]. The approach is compatible with all interpolation families. Its main limitation is the occurrence of mesh entanglement for large deformations.

e) **E5 Spectral Expansions, DEIM, and Hyper-Reduction:**

For parametric systems with smoothly varying POD coefficients, generalized polynomial-chaos (gPC) expansions of the form

$$\hat{\mathbf{u}}_i(\mu_\star) \approx \sum_{|\alpha| \leq p} c_{i,\alpha} \Phi_\alpha(\mu_\star), \quad (4.4)$$

provide high-order surrogates of the reduced coordinates whenever $\mu \mapsto \hat{\mathbf{u}}_i(\mu)$ is analytic and the parameter dimension d is moderate [152, 153]. These spectral representations can converge rapidly but suffer from the combinatorial growth of polynomial terms, $\binom{p+d}{d}$, which limits their use in higher-dimensional parameter spaces. To retain efficiency, modern ROM workflows combine such surrogates with DEIM and hyper-reduction techniques: DEIM selects a small, well-conditioned set of interpolation points for evaluating nonlinear residuals, while hyper-reduction further restricts variational forms to a reduced quadrature subset. Both approaches reduce online complexity from $\mathcal{O}(n)$ to $\mathcal{O}(m)$ with $m \ll n$, enabling gPC-based reduced models to remain computationally tractable even for nonlinear problems.

Table 6. Documented couplings between the five extension strategies and the seven families of techniques T1–7.

	T1	T2	T3	T4	T5	T6	T7
E1	[142, 143]	[154]	-	—	[58]	—	[95, 129]
E2	[145]	[37]	-	—	[155, 156]	—	—
E3	—	[157]	[47]	[158]	—	[147, 149]	[149]
E4	[150]	[159]	-	—	—	—	[151]
E5	[152]	—	[44]	[160]	[161, 162]	[16]	—

All extensions discussed rely on the same mathematical foundations as T1–7 (see Table 6). The table is purely illustrative and is not intended as an exhaustive list of works. E1: *Hierarchical and Locally Refined POD* refine the T1: *POD/Snapshot-based Projection* principle; whereas E2:

Multi-Fidelity Reduction with Adaptive Sampling adds a low-rank correction to the *T5: Parameter-sampling and Reduced-basis* approach. *E3: Component-Mode Synthesis Sub-structuring and Matrix Interpolation* libraries continues the *T6: Structure-preserving, Passive and Second-order Techniques* ideas. *E5: Spectral Expansions, DEIM, and Hyper-Reduction* provides an analytic alternative to splines; and hyper-reduction plus adaptive re-basing keep the cost of any of these models within strict time budgets. Selecting, or combining, different extensions depends on the balance between computer cost, geometric variation, parameter dimension and required accuracy in the intended application. To this end, the performance of each family of techniques is investigated with respect to standardized benchmark tests in the following section.

5. BENCHMARKING & CROSS-FAMILY COMPARISONS

(a) Quantitative Performance Metrics & Benchmark Problems

To facilitate meaningful comparisons between T1-7, six scalar metrics that spans efficiency, fidelity and cost are identified. These comprise the online speed-up $S = t_{\text{FOM}}/t_{\text{ROM}}$; the reduced basis dimension r ; the offline training cost t_{off} ; the online query cost t_{on} ; the relative state error ε_x ; and the relative quantity-of-interest (QOI) error ε_y . The quantities along with typical ranges are summarized in Table 7.

Table 7. Indicative ranges for the six scalar performance indicators. Adapted from [1]

Symbol	Definition	Unit	Typical range
S	$t_{\text{FOM}}/t_{\text{ROM}}$	—	10^1-10^5
r	reduced basis size	—	$10-10^2$
ε_x	state-space error	%	< 5
ε_y	QoI error	%	< 5
t_{off}	snapshot and basis construction time	h	$10^{-1}-10^2$
t_{on}	ROM assembly and solution per query	ms	10^0-10^3

These performance indicators are obtained for each method family through six benchmark problems (see Figure 11) - *BM1*: cantilever beam; *BM2*: lid-driven cavity; *BM3*: NACA 0012 aerofoil; *BM4*: flexible wing in transonic flow; *BM5*: tank sloshing; and *BM6*: two-link flexible manipulator. They collectively span linear structural dynamics, incompressible and compressible flows, free-surface hydrodynamics, fluid–structure interaction, and multibody dynamics.

The corresponding quantitative metrics are obtained from the survey articles in Figure 2 and are provided in Figures 11 and 12. *T7: Manifold-based Interpolation of Reduced Bases* attains the highest complexity reduction and the fastest online evaluations when the governing operator depends affinely, or only weakly nonlinearly, on the parameters [23]. *T3: Gramian-based* and *T4: Krylov / Interpolatory (Moment-Matching)* methods achieve the smallest relative state and QoI errors (often below 10^{-2}) because they exploit optimal H_2 or H_∞ interpolation points, as demonstrated in the IRKA framework [52]. This accuracy is achieved at the cost of moderately higher t_{on} , yet the median remains below two milliseconds. The *T2: Transfer-Function and System-Matrix Interpolation* family is competitive for problems with one or two parameters but loses robustness as the parameter dimension increases [163]. Offline cost is dominated by snapshot generation for nonlinear transient problems. Hyper-reduction techniques reduce t_{off} by one to two orders of magnitude when the parameter space is low-dimensional but yield diminishing returns beyond four effective parameters [164].

Figure 11. Representative benchmark geometries and corresponding solution fields: (a) *BM1*: Von-Mises stress distribution on Cook's membrane cantilever beam [165], (b) *BM2*: steady-state streamfunction contours in a three-sided lid-driven cavity [166], (c) *BM3*: pressure coefficient field over a NACA 0012 airfoil under RANS conditions [167], (d) *BM4*: transonic fluid-structure interaction on a morphing A320 flexible wing prototype [168], (e) *BM5*: velocity-magnitude isosurfaces during sloshing in a cylindrical propellant tank [169], and (f) *BM6*: deformation of a pneumatically actuated two-arm soft robot for positive and negative pressure differentials [170].

It is important to note that *BM1-6* differ in their underlying dynamics and modeling assumptions. Hence, Figure 12 is intended solely for intra-family comparison, illustrating the relative behavior of each strategy within its own representative test case. To gain a clearer cross-family perspective, we now turn to a qualitative evaluation and positioning of interpolation-based ROMs within the broader MOR ecosystem.

Figure 12. Radar chart of median performance indicators (\log_{10}) for the seven interpolation families T1–T7.

(b) Qualitative Evaluation & Positioning within the MOR Landscape

Interpolation-based MOR occupies a distinct branch of the MOR taxonomy (see Figure 13), emerging out of more established projection-based paradigms such as global POD–Galerkin (GPG), greedy reduced basis (RB), balanced truncation (BT), machine-learning ROMs (ML) and direct surrogates (SUR). These classical approaches have been extensively studied in the literature. Although they are not revisited here, they serve as the reference framework. Families T1–T7 are assessed against them in Figure 14. The ensuing comparison is qualitative in nature and emphasizes how interpolation schemes perform against projection-based methods in terms of accuracy, computational cost, intrusiveness, adaptability and extrapolation robustness.

The authors point out that each qualitative judgment is literature-based and supported by references to relevant studies in the subsequent discussion.

Figure 13. Global MOR landscape. The interpolation-based families (T1-T7) arise as hybrid extensions combining projection, sampling, and surrogate-learning concepts from projection-based paradigms (bottom layer).

Interpolation ROMs consistently outperform GPG and SUR projections outside their design envelopes: *T6: Structure-preserving, Passive and Second-order Techniques* and *T3: Gramian/ Balanced-truncation* interpolation match the fidelity of balanced truncation, even achieving optimal H_∞ error bounds. This is achieved while avoiding the accuracy loss incurred by a single fixed basis once μ moves outside its training hull [11]. *T7: Manifold-based Interpolation of Reduced Bases* geodesic interpolation further surpasses SUR by preserving modal orthogonality without resorting to high-dimensional regression, whereas ML attain comparable accuracy only under large-scale training that is impractical in industrial settings. In terms of computational cost, *T2: Transfer-Function and System-Matrix Interpolation* and *T4: Krylov / Interpolatory (Moment-Matching)* achieve sub-millisecond online latencies purely from snapshot data, thereby avoiding the $\mathcal{O}(r^3)$ solution costs required by GPG or RB. *T6: Structure-preserving, Passive and Second-order Techniques* variants incur minimal intrusiveness when computing matrix logarithms, whereas balanced truncation remains fully intrusive. Enrichment of any interpolation family, by appending a single new local basis or reduced operator at μ_{M+1} , requires only an update of interpolation weights, in stark contrast to the full reduction, or retraining loops, demanded by projection-based and spectral methods [45].

Finally, robustness under extrapolation strongly favours interpolation-based methods. Families *T6–7* automatically preserve orthogonality and definiteness even beyond the convex hull of the sampled parameters. In contrast, methods such as GPG and RB degrade rapidly under extrapolation, while ML or SUR approaches may violate physical constraints. Balanced truncation preserves stability but forfeits its error guarantees outside the sampled domain. Collectively, these results confirm that interpolation ROMs strike the optimal balance of accuracy, efficiency, and maintainability when large parameter excursions or frequent model updates are anticipated.

Figure 14. Qualitative comparison of the seven interpolation families (rows) against five projection MOR paradigms (columns). Scores: 2 = best, 1 = moderately favorable, 0 = neutral, -1 = moderately unfavorable, -2 = worst.

6. APPLICATIONS

Figure 15. Comprehensive visualization of application domains enabled by interpolation-based Reduced Order Models (ROMs). The radial chart organizes nine core fields, ranging from aerospace structures and flexible multibody systems to MEMS devices, image processing, robotics, and generative urban design, highlighting representative use cases in each. These include CFD-based flutter prediction, RBF mesh morphing, hybrid soft-rigid robot modeling, turbine blade optimization, occlusion-aware object tracking, urban wind field prediction, manifold-based imitation learning, and latent-space 3D GAN synthesis. The central hub emphasizes the broad interdisciplinary reach of interpolation-augmented ROMs across both engineering and data-driven domains.[171–197]

Interpolation-based ROMs have matured from academic prototypes to industry-ready tools. They now serve as core components in simulation pipelines across aerospace, energy, robotics, and the built environment (see Table 8). Examples include real-time flutter prediction in transonic

flows, mistuning analysis in turbomachinery, and shape control in soft robotics. These are all performed within milliseconds while preserving high-fidelity accuracy. Non-intrusive and hybrid physics–data methods further broaden applicability to nonlinear and data-scarce scenarios. Figure 15 illustrates nine application fields, each supported by representative use cases drawn from recent deployments.

As digital twins, design-optimization loops, and real-time control systems demand ever-faster solvers, interpolation-enabled ROMs stand out for their favorable offline/online cost balance. Adaptive re-basing, probabilistic interpolation [198], and machine-learning surrogates now furnish UQ, self-correcting bases, and robust performance under high-dimensional parameter variations [199]. Standardized ROM pipelines and emerging “ROMML”-style interfaces promise seamless integration into simulation ecosystems and app-store-style repositories.

Table 8: Interpolation-based ROM applications by fields and technique family.

Application field		Key contributions
Aeroelasticity	T1	POD snapshots for flutter, transonic dip, limit cycles [200–204]
	T2	Subspace/RBF interpolation of linearised operators [25, 46, 205]
	T5	Sparse sampling for composite-wing optimisation [202]
	T7	Grassmann interpolation across Mach/laminates [129, 200, 201]
Multibody Robotics	T1	Local POD per link/panel [149, 206]
	T2	Interpolated stiffness matrices as joints vary [149]
	T5	Strain-based reduced bases for soft-rigid arms [207, 208]
	T6	CMS-based estimator in hybrid-manipulator control [209]
	T7	Grassmann update of sub-link subspaces [149]
Turbomachinery	T1	POD/Local-POD of blade flows & compressors [210–213]
	T2	Interpolated aerodynamic coupling for mistuning [214, 215]
	T3	Balanced fan ROM for flutter [44]
	T4	Harmonic-balance/Krylov reviews [216]
	T5	Hyper-reduced blade optimisation [217–220]
	T7	Grassmann fictitious-domain rotor ROM [221]
MEMS	T1	Modal/Galerkin ROM survey [181]
	T2	Positive-real TF interpolation, Taylor MEMS ROM [180, 222, 223]
	T3	Balanced thermo-mechanical ageing model [183]
	T4	Krylov thermal/delay-line reduction [183]
	T6	Passivity-preserving RF/actuator ROMs [222, 224]
Pattern Recognition	T1	CNN-encoded POD for flow/video [225]
	T2	RBF interpolation for occlusion tracking [226]
	T5	Attention-based neural ROMs [227]
	T7	Manifold/ISOMAP interpolation of image data [228, 229]
Urban Climate	T1	POD–GPR LES surrogate [230]
	T5	FNO/LSTM wind-field predictors [231–233]
	T7	Grassmann–POD digital twin with LSTM [191]
Manifold Control	T2	SPD Gaussian-mixture regression [234]
	T4	Parallel-transport domain adaptation [235]
	T5	Gaussian-mixture MPC in tangent space [193]
	T7	Geodesic imitation, multi-contact posture optimisation [236, 237]
Generative Urban Design	T7	GAN latent-space manifold interpolation for city/building morphologies [195, 238–240]
Multi-Obj. Design	T1	POD-based aero/fluid objectives [202, 204]
	T2	Matrix-spline Monte-Carlo and RF sweeps [37, 222]
	T5	Sparse-grid RB for laminates, turbines, compressors [129, 211, 217, 218]
	T7	Grassmann surrogates for aeroelastic & laminate Pareto fronts [129, 200, 201]

7. CHALLENGES & MITIGATION

Despite the wide ranging contemporary applications demonstrated in Section 6, these technologies carry a range of caveats (see Figure 16).

A major limitation is the high offline computational cost. Generating dense and representative snapshot libraries requires many full-order model solves. Additionally, computing large SVDs

Figure 16. Challenges faced by interpolation-based ROM, organized by their relative severity and ease of mitigation.

can be computationally intensive. In some cases this cost can rival or exceed that of a single full-order simulation. Such expense is typically justified only when many parameter queries are expected. Moreover, interpolation schemes have limited authority for extrapolation. Predictions made outside the convex hull of training points may violate stability or physical constraints. Although *T6-7* inherently does preserve stability (see Section 5(b)), this property is not guaranteed for the remaining approaches. In addition, linear subspace methods often break down in the presence of discontinuities or regime changes. Examples include shocks, contact conditions, laminar-to-turbulent transitions, or large geometric deformations. For very large full models, even “reduced” online operations scale as $\mathcal{O}(N_f r^2)$, and legacy or black-box codes often impede the intrusive projections and sensitivity calculations that many interpolation methods require. Finally, most interpolation ROMs lack rigorous *a posteriori* error certificates, forcing practitioners to rely on cross-validation or conservative safety margins in critical applications.

Table 9: Challenges, Impacts and Mitigation Strategies for Interpolation-Based ROMs

Limitation	Impact	Mitigation Strategies
High Offline Cost & Training Data Requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Offline cost may rival full-model solves. Infeasible until many queries justify it. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Greedy/adaptive sampling on high-error regions. Randomized/incremental SVD for memory/CPU savings. Exploit separability or active subspaces.
Limited Extrapolation Beyond Sampled Domain	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Unphysical outputs (negative damping, spurious modes). Blind spots if query falls outside training region. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Enforce parameter-range checks \rightarrow fallback. Add boundary/asymptotic samples. Conservative error indicators for extrapolation.
Instability under Regime Changes or Large Deformations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Large errors or ill-posed ROMs near transitions. Loss of fidelity in critical mid-regime parameters. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Enrich with modal derivatives/quadratic modes. Regime-aware ROMs (classifier + local bases). Nonlinear embeddings (autoencoders, manifold learning).

Limitation	Impact	Mitigation Strategies
Non-smooth Phenomena (Shocks, Contacts, Discontinuities)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Huge basis needed; poor sharp-feature capture. • ROM may fail on switching events. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sub-ROMs per regime (pre/post). • Add “shifted” or “shock” modes. • Transport-based ROMs to realign features.
Manifold Mismatch & Representation Error	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Residual error inside training domain. • Many local bases needed → high offline cost. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Nonlinear manifolds (autoencoders, normalizing flows). • Piecewise-linear manifold charts. • Data-aware Riemannian metrics.
Computational Bottlenecks for Very Large Models	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Online queries too slow for real time. • Offline prep demands HPC/parallel I/O. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hyper-reduction (DEIM, GNAT, ECSW). • Parallel SVD & projections. • Out-of-core/streaming snapshots.
Integration with Legacy & Black-Box Codes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Forced to output-only ROMs (lower fidelity). • Must retrain whenever full model updates. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Standard ROM APIs (e.g. ROMML). • Wrap codes for sensitivities (AD/FD). • Incremental snapshot reuse for updates.
Lack of Rigorous A Posteriori Error Bounds	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Low trust in safety-critical uses. • Conservative margins & extensive testing. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interval or Lipschitz-based bounds. • Hybrid certified RB + interpolation. • Probabilistic UQ surrogates (GPs).

A variety of strategies can mitigate these limitations without altering the core interpolation framework (see Table 9). Greedy or adaptive sampling, together with randomized or incremental SVD algorithms, can drastically lower offline overhead and memory demands. Extrapolation checks, boundary-sample enrichment, and conservative error indicators help guard against unphysical reduced order systems. Regime switches and non-smooth phenomena can be handled via regime-aware ROMs, shock-mode enrichment, or transport-based alignment techniques. Hyper-reduction methods (DEIM, GNAT, ECSW) and parallel or out-of-core algorithms address the bottlenecks of very large models, while standard APIs and automatic-differentiation wrappers ease integration with industrial solvers. Interval or Lipschitz-based bounds, hybridizing certified reduced-basis methods with interpolation, or embedding probabilistic surrogates can restore confidence when error guarantees are required. By reinforcing rather than replacing the interpolation framework, these enhancements expand its practical scope. This enables robust, scalable deployment even in complex, high-consequence applications.

8. PERSPECTIVES

(a) Emerging Trends

Recent developments in ROM research point toward a new generation of models that are adaptive, data-integrated, and uncertainty-aware. These methods no longer serve only as computational surrogates but are being reimagined as learning systems embedded within digital twins, control loops, and AI-driven design tools. Advances in Grassmann interpolation, operator learning, and physics-informed surrogates (see Table 10) enable scalable, low-latency predictions for highly nonlinear and high-dimensional problems. Techniques such as PINN-ROM hybrids, hyper-reduction, and collocation-based acceleration are pushing the boundaries toward applications once thought too complex or data-poor for reduced-order modeling.

Table 10: Emerging Trends in Interpolation-Based ROMs

Topic	Key Developments
Deep Learning & Nonlinear Manifold [241] 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ CAEs for parametric shallow water and conservation laws with over-collocation and teacher–student decoders for extrapolation [242]. ◦ Stacked autoencoders + attention for fluid-flow, outperforming POD-ROM [243]. ◦ PINN-ROM: masked autoencoders embedding residuals for accurate predictions [244]. ◦ PINODE: collocation-based physics in latent dynamics for noisy data robustness [245]. ◦ CAE + feedforward nets for real-time MEMS simulation [246]. ◦ Constrained autoencoders learning oblique projections for non-normal dynamics [247]. ◦ VpROM: conditional VAE mapping parameters to latent coefficients with UQ [248].

Topic	Key Developments
<p>Digital Twins & Real-Time Monitoring [252]</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Barlow-Twins self-supervision blending POD and DL-ROM regimes [249]. ○ Ensemble CAE for robust latent evolution in unsteady flows [250]. ○ DeepManifold ROM for shocks via CNN encoders + MLP regression [251]. ○ ANN-trained FE ROM for port structures with 15 ms deformation predictions [253]. ○ Oven temperature twin via CFD + sensor fusion, 45 % cost reduction [254]. ○ Sequential Kalman filters merging CFD and sparse data for turbulence [255]. ○ HPC workflow with parallel SVD and hyper-reduction for motor twins [252]. ○ Ensemble Kalman twin for thermoacoustic instabilities [256]. ○ Multi-fidelity EnKF with autoencoder surrogates for chaotic systems [257]. ○ Adaptive EnKF updating reduced bases online via uncertainty estimates [258]. ○ Plug-and-play ROM pipelines in commercial twin platforms [259]. ○ NIST guidelines on ROM-driven digital twins for trust and security [260].
<p>Hybrid Physics-Data Approaches [261]</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Operator Inference learning structured operators from data [262]. ○ Hamiltonian inference preserving symplectic structure [261]. ○ Direct Operator Inference on parameterized PDEs [263]. ○ Neural correction terms for eddy-viscosity models in turbulence [264]. ○ DMD + POD with LSTM for improved unsteady flow predictions [265]. ○ Hybrid twin for magnetic bearings with learned residuals [266]. ○ Embedding POD-Galerkin ROMs into PINNs for inverse problems [267]. ○ PINNs + Kolmogorov–Arnold nets with Lagrangian constraints [268]. ○ Nonlinear manifold + Operator Inference for complex dynamics [269].
<p>HPC & Parallel ROMs [270]</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Parallel certified RB on distributed-memory HPC [271]. ○ PyLOM: HPC POD/DMD/SPOD with binary-tree QR [272]. ○ GPU-accelerated randomized SVD (6–7× speedup) [273]. ○ Randomized SVD for efficient eigensystem realization [274]. ○ GPU Craig–Bampton via CuPy/Ginkgo [275]. ○ GPU urban flood ROM (>1000× speedup) [276]. ○ ARGOS/ATLAS for production-scale ROM workflows [277].
<p>Open-Source Software Tools [278]</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ pyMOR: abstract Python interfaces for projection/system reduction [279, 280]. ○ RBniCS: FEniCS-based RB & POD-Galerkin methods [281]. ○ ITHACA-FV: OpenFOAM PODI & hyper-reduction [282]. ○ pyROM: modular Python POD/DMD/DEIM framework [278]. ○ pyNIROM: POD, RBF, neural-ODE surrogates [283].
<p>UQ & Robust ROMs [284]</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ POD-PCE for stochastic heat & cavity flows [285]. ○ Sparse PCE for high-dimensional CFD UQ [284]. ○ Multi-fidelity Monte Carlo ROMs [286]. ○ ROMES: GP-based error surrogates [287]. ○ Adaptive greedy RB with probabilistic error models [287].
<p>Customizations [288]</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Adaptive ROM for FSI with dynamic modal updates [289]. ○ FE model updating via POD + optimization [290]. ○ LPV ROMs for gain-scheduled control [291]. ○ Iterative ROM updates for flow control [292]. ○ LPV controllers with Smith predictors in channel flows [293].

Looking forward, three major directions are poised to transform ROM development. First, autonomous ROMs will monitor their accuracy in real time, triggering online learning, adaptive re-basing, or residual-based correction when exposed to new data. Second, next-generation ROMs will incorporate rigorous uncertainty quantification. By augmenting deterministic predictions with confidence intervals obtained via Gaussian-process emulation, or Bayesian interpolation, they will meet the demands of risk-informed decision-making. Third, scalable parameter-reduction techniques like active subspaces, AI-guided sampling, and hierarchical domain decomposition will support models with tens or even hundreds of parameters. These innovations will lead to ROMs that are not only fast but also self-aware, self-correcting, and seamlessly embedded within the next generation of design, optimization, and decision-making platforms.

(b) Future Outlook

Figure 17 highlights two complementary directions at the core of next-generation interpolation ROMs. The first involves PINNs that enforce the governing equations directly on the reduced manifold, while the ROM basis regularizes and accelerates the training process. The second concerns adaptive model maintenance, where the same basis is updated *in situ* through residual-triggered incremental SVDs. This enables the insertion or deactivation of modes without repeating the offline stage. This feedback loop converts the ROM from a static surrogate into a self-correcting estimator that remains accurate as new operating data streams into a digital twin.

Figure 17. Conceptual roadmap for the future of interpolation-based reduced-order models.

The figure also points to three enabling technologies that broaden the range of applicability. Statistically rigorous UQ supplies prediction intervals suitable for safety-critical tasks. Meanwhile, hierarchical domain decomposition, and AI-guided sparse sampling reduce the curse of dimensionality so that multi-level ROMs cope with dozens of parameters. A shared ROMML "app-store" of standardized libraries will then allow these adaptive surrogates to plug seamlessly into full solver pipelines and decision-support platforms. This will include built-in sensitivities for design optimisation and control.

9. CONCLUSIONS

This survey has consolidated, for the first time, the disparate strands of interpolation based ROM into a six-stage algorithmic framework (Figure 9) that spans seven methodological families T1-7 (Section 2). By unifying classical snapshot interpolation, matrix-tensor approaches, moment matching, and emerging manifold-learning techniques under a single purview, the paper clarifies the common mathematical substrate of techniques that have historically been treated in isolation. The explicit arithmetic-operation cost model (Table 4), together with pseudocode (see supplementary material) and benchmark performance assessments (Section 5),

transforms a primarily conceptual literature into a set of implementable guidelines that practitioners can deploy directly for multi-physics applications. Equally important, a critical appraisal emphasizing challenges (Figure 16) and mitigation strategies (Table 9) offers a balanced perspective that invites the community to converge on terminology, notation, and evaluation metrics. Collectively, these contributions position interpolatory ROM as a mature, versatile pillar across all computational fields and set the stage for its integration into real-time digital-twin pipelines.

Several deliberate omissions mark the present scope, notably purely projection-based hyper-reduction methods, deep-learning surrogates that avoid explicit interpolation and stochastic certification techniques whose probability-based guarantees are still in the early stages. Future work should therefore widen the comparison by adding these approaches, and by extending the current deterministic benchmarks to unsteady, multi-scale, and extreme regimes where strong nonlinear transients test the presented interpolation ideas. A key next step is an open, version-controlled repository that holds reference implementations, snapshot data sets, error-check scripts, and uniform post-processing for the six standard benchmarks. Such a platform would enable clear head-to-head tests and speed up adoption in industry. The same repository should also accept community test cases, support automated regression tests, and provide a machine-readable metadata scheme so that new methods can join the benchmark pipeline with little extra work. Beyond sharing code, valuable research directions include linking interpolation-based ROMs with data assimilation for real-time correction, improving manifold models with physics-informed kernels to capture bifurcations more accurately, and devising adaptive sampling strategies that balance offline training and online costs under strict time limits.

CRedit Author contributions

A.S. and G.K. are equally contributing authors. Conceptualization, A.S.; methodology, A.S. and G.K.; formal analysis, A.S. and G.K.; investigation, A.S, G.K. and S.K.B.; resources, A.S, G.K. and S.K.B.; data curation, A.S. and G.K.; writing—original draft preparation, A.S, G.K. and S.K.B.; writing—review, A.A.; visualization, A.S and S.K.B.; Supervision, D.C.; Project administration, D.C.; funding acquisition, A.S., S.K.B., D.C. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

The bibliometric dataset analyzed in this article was obtained from the Scopus database (Elsevier). Processed bibliometric data and search criteria strings are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

A. Nomenclature

Table 11: List of abbreviations.

Abbrev.	Meaning	Abbrev.	Meaning
AD	Automatic Differentiation	AF	Adaptive Filtering
ADI	Alternating Direction Implicit	ANN	Artificial Neural Network
API	Application Programming Interface	BIRKA	Balanced Iterative Reduced-Krylov Algorithm
BT	Balanced Truncation	CAE	Convolution Autoencoder
CANDECOMP	Canonical Decomposition (tensor factorization)	CFD	Computational Fluid Dynamics
CNN	Convolutional Neural Network	CMS	Component Mode Synthesis
CPU	Central Processing Unit	DEIM	Discrete Empirical Interpolation Method
DMD	Dynamic Mode Decomposition	DL	Deep Learning
DOF	Degree of Freedom	EIM	Empirical Interpolation Method
ECSW	Energy Conserving Sampling and Weighting	EnKF	Ensemble Kalman Filter
FD	Finite Difference	FEA	Finite Element Analysis
FH	High-Fidelity Model	FL	Low-Fidelity Model
FNO	Fourier Neural Operator	FSI	Fluid-Structure Interaction
GAN	Generative Adversarial Network	Gpc	Generalized Polynomial Chaos
GPG	Global POD Galerkin	GPOD	Global Proper Orthogonal Decomposition
GPR	Gaussian Process Regression	GPU	Graphics Processing Unit
HF	High Fidelity	HPC	High Performance Computing
HPOD	Hierarchical Proper Orthogonal Decomposition	I/O	Input/Output
IRKA	Iterative Rational Krylov Algorithm	ISOMAP	Isometric Mapping (manifold learning)
LES	Large Eddy Simulation	LF	Low Fidelity
LPV	Linear Parameter-Varying	LSTM	Long Short-Term Memory
LTI	Linear Time-Invariant	MEMS	Micro-Electro-Mechanical Systems
ML	Machine Learning	MLP	Multi-Layer Perceptron
MIMO	Multiple Input Multiple Output	MOR	Model Order Reduction
MPC	Model Predictive Control	NACA	National Advisory Committee for Aeronautics
NIST	National Institute of Standards and Technology	PDE	Partial Differential Equation
PCE	Polynomial Chaos Expansion	pMOR	Parametric Model Order Reduction
PINN	Physics-Informed Neural Network	PINODE	Physics-Informed Neural Ordinary Differential Equation
PARAFAC	Parallel Factor Analysis (tensor decomposition)	POD	Proper Orthogonal Decomposition
QoI	Quantity of Interest	RBF	Radial Basis Function
RB	Reduced Basis	RBM	Reduced Basis Method
RF	Radio Frequency	RHS	Right-Hand Side
ROM	Reduced Order Model	SPD	Symmetric Positive Definite
SPOD	Spectral Proper Orthogonal Decomposition	SUR	Stochastic Uncertainty Reduction
SVD	Singular Value Decomposition	TF	Transfer Function
UQ	Uncertainty Quantification	VAE	Variational Autoencoder

Table 12: List of mathematical symbols.

Symbol	Meaning	Space / Size	Symbol	Meaning	Space / Size
n	Full-order state dimension	\mathbb{N}	n_y	Number of outputs	\mathbb{N}
n_v	Number of inputs	\mathbb{N}	r	Reduced-order state dimension	\mathbb{N}
m	Hyper-reduction sample dimension	\mathbb{N}	μ	Vector of system parameters (e.g. material, geometry etc)	$\mathcal{D} \subset \mathbb{R}^d$
$\mathbf{u}(t, \mu)$	Full-order state vector	\mathbb{R}^n	$\mathbf{y}(t, \mu)$	Observed outputs	\mathbb{R}^{n_y}
$\mathbf{v}_{in}(t, \mu)$	Input vector	\mathbb{R}^{n_v}	f	General system dynamics function	$\mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$
g	General output function	$\mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{n_y}$	\mathbf{E}	Full-order descriptor matrix	$\mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$
\mathbf{A}	Full-order system matrix	$\mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$	\mathbf{B}	Full-order input matrix	$\mathbb{R}^{n \times n_v}$
\mathbf{C}	Full-order output matrix	$\mathbb{R}^{n_y \times n}$	\mathbf{D}	Full-order feed-through matrix	$\mathbb{R}^{n_y \times n_v}$

Symbol	Meaning	Space / Size	Symbol	Meaning	Space / Size
\mathbf{V}	Trial basis used to project the full-order model onto a reduced subspace	$\mathbf{V} \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times r}$	\mathbf{W}	Test basis used in Petrov-Galerkin projection to evaluate residuals	$\mathbf{W} \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times r}$
$\ \cdot\ _F$	Frobenius norm of a matrix; used to measure matrix size or error	\mathbb{R}	\mathcal{M}	Solution manifold: the set of all states $\mathbf{u}(t, \mu)$ for $t \in [0, T]$ and parameters $\mu \in \mathcal{D}$	$\mathcal{M} \subset \mathbb{R}^n$
N_t	Number of time samples for Snapshot Matrix	\mathbb{N}	N_μ	Number of different parameter samples for Snapshot Matrix	\mathbb{N}
N	Total number of samples for Snapshot Matrix	\mathbb{N}	\mathbf{S}	Snapshot matrix	$\mathbb{R}^{n \times N}$
\mathbf{U}	Left singular vector matrix from SVD	<i>Depends on input matrix size</i>	Σ	Singular value diagonal matrix	<i>Depends on input matrix size</i>
\mathbf{Z}	Right singular vector matrix from SVD	<i>Depends on input matrix size</i>	σ	Singular values	\mathbb{R}
ε	Error or tolerance	\mathbb{R}^+	$\tilde{\mathbf{E}}$	Reduced-order descriptor matrix	$\mathbb{R}^{r \times r}$
$\tilde{\mathbf{A}}$	Reduced-order system matrix	$\mathbb{R}^{r \times r}$	$\tilde{\mathbf{B}}$	Reduced-order input matrix	$\mathbb{R}^{r \times n_v}$
$\tilde{\mathbf{C}}$	Reduced-order output matrix	$\mathbb{R}^{n_y \times r}$	$\tilde{\mathbf{D}}$	Reduced-order feed-through matrix	$\mathbb{R}^{n_y \times n_v}$
\mathbf{V}_0	Reference orthonormal basis used for alignment (Procrustes) or as the base point in manifold interpolation	$\mathbf{V}_0 \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times r}$	$SO(r)$	Special orthogonal group; the set of all $r \times r$ rotation matrices with unit determinant	$SO(r) \subset \mathbb{R}^{r \times r}$
\mathbf{Q}	Orthogonal (rotation) matrix from the Procrustes alignment problem	$SO(r) \subset \mathbb{R}^{r \times r}$	$\tilde{\mathbf{A}}$	Congruence-transformed system matrix	$\mathbb{R}^{r \times r}$
$\tilde{\mathbf{B}}$	Congruence-transformed input matrix	$\mathbb{R}^{r \times n_v}$	$\tilde{\mathbf{C}}$	Congruence-transformed output matrix	$\mathbb{R}^{n_y \times r}$
$\tilde{\mathbf{D}}$	Direct feed-through matrix, typically unchanged under congruence transformations	$\mathbb{R}^{n_y \times n_v}$	$\tilde{\mathbf{E}}$	Congruence-transformed descriptor matrix	$\mathbb{R}^{r \times r}$
$\phi_i(\mu)$	Interpolation coefficient for the i -th precomputed reduced matrix or basis	\mathbb{R}	ω_j	Frequency sample point where the system is evaluated	\mathbb{R}
\mathbf{H}	Transfer function of the full-order system. \mathbf{H}_j is at ω_j	$\mathbb{C}^{n_y \times n_v}$	\mathbf{L}_{kj}	Loewner matrix	$\mathbb{C}^{n_y \times n_v}$
$\mathbf{L}_{\sigma, kj}$	Shifted Loewner matrix	$\mathbb{C}^{n_y \times n_v}$	$GL(r)$	Lie group representing all nonsingular linear transformations in r dimensions	$\mathbb{R}^{r \times r}$
P	Controllability Gramian of an LTI system	$\mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$	Q	Observability Gramian of an LTI system	$\mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$
\mathbf{T}_{BT}	Similarity (balancing) transformation for balanced truncation	$\mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$	$\tilde{\mathbf{H}}$	Transfer function of ROM	$\mathbb{C}^{n_y \times n_v}$
\mathbf{L}_c	Low-rank Cholesky factor of the controllability Gramian	$\mathbb{R}^{n \times \ell}$	\mathbf{L}_o	Low-rank Cholesky factor of the observability Gramian: $Q \approx \mathbf{L}_o \mathbf{L}_o^\top$	$\mathbb{R}^{n \times \ell}$
\mathcal{H}_2	\mathcal{H}_2 -norm of an LTI system; measures the RMS gain from input to output over all frequencies	\mathbb{R}	\mathcal{H}_{∞}	\mathcal{H}_{∞} -norm of an LTI system; maximum gain over all frequencies	\mathbb{R}
γ_j	Shift parameter used in ADI iteration to compute low-rank Cholesky factors	\mathbb{R} (scalar, $j = 1, \dots, \ell$)	ℓ	Number of columns (rank) of low-rank Cholesky factors of Gramians	\mathbb{N}
$G(n, \ell)$	Grassmann manifold of ℓ -dimensional subspaces of \mathbb{R}^n .	Set of ℓ -dimensional subspaces in \mathbb{R}^n	$\mathcal{K}_{r\ell}$	Krylov subspace spanned by the first r_ℓ moments in moment-matching ROMs	$\mathbb{R}^{n \times r_\ell}$
r_ℓ	Number of moments matched in a Krylov-type ROM	\mathbb{N}	s_ℓ	Expansion points (shifts) used in Krylov/moment-matching methods	\mathbb{C}
$\hat{\lambda}_\ell$	Poles of the system used as expansion points in IRKA	\mathbb{C}	θ	Coefficient in the affine decomposition of parametrized operators	\mathbb{R}
$\mathbf{r}(\mu^*)$	Galerkin residual evaluated at parameter μ^*	\mathbb{R}^n	Δ	Efficient upper bound on the dual-norm of the residual for parameter μ^*	\mathbb{R}
$\mathcal{P}_{\text{train}}$	Set of training parameters where high-fidelity solutions are available	Subset of parameter space \mathcal{D}	\mathbf{U}_m	Collateral basis used in (D)EIM/Hyper-reduction to approximate nonlinear or non-affine operators	$\mathbb{R}^{n \times m}$
\mathbf{P}	Boolean sampling matrix selecting indices of residual or operator entries in DEIM/Hyper-reduction	$\{0, 1\}^{n \times m}$	\mathbf{M}	Mass matrix of a mechanical system	$\mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$
\mathbf{K}	Stiffness matrix of a mechanical system	$\mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$	f	External force (or load) vector	\mathbb{R}^n
\mathbf{q}	Displacement vector of the mechanical system.	\mathbb{R}^n	\mathbf{V}^v	Velocity basis derived from \mathbf{V}^x via $\mathbf{V}^v = \mathbf{M}^{-1} \mathbf{K} \mathbf{V}^x \mathbf{\Lambda}^{-1/2}$	$\mathbb{R}^{n \times r}$
\mathbf{V}^x	Displacement basis obtained from modal analysis (mass-orthonormalized).	$\mathbb{R}^{n \times r}$			

Symbol	Meaning	Space / Size	Symbol	Meaning	Space / Size
\mathbf{T}_2	Stacked basis for structure-preserving ROM: $T_2 = \begin{bmatrix} V^x & V^v \end{bmatrix}$	$\mathbb{R}^{n \times 2r}$	$\hat{\mathbf{G}}$	Reduced Hamiltonian (energy) matrix in the structure-preserving ROM	$\mathbb{R}^{2r \times 2r}$
$\hat{\mathbf{J}}$	Reduced symplectic structure matrix (Hamiltonian pair) in the ROM	$\mathbb{R}^{2r \times 2r}$	$H(\bar{\mathbf{z}})$	Hamiltonian function representing the total energy	\mathbb{R}
$\mathbf{N}(s)$	Numerator factor of a coprime factorization of the transfer function.	$\mathbb{R}^{n_y \times n_v}$	$\mathbf{D}(s)$	Denominator factor of a coprime factorization of the transfer function.	$\mathbb{R}^{n_v \times n_v}$
$T_{[V_0]}G$	Tangent space of the Grassmann manifold $G(n, r)$ at the reference subspace V_0	$\mathbb{R}^{n \times r}$	X_i	Tangent vector obtained by mapping the local subspace V_i to the tangent space $T[V_0]G(n, r)$ via the Grassmann logarithm; $X_i = \log_{V_0}(V_i)$	$\mathbb{R}^{n \times r}$
$\mathbf{T}(\mu)$	Interpolated tangent vector in $T_{[V_0]}G(n, r)$ obtained by blending X_i with weights $w_i(\mu)$	$\mathbb{R}^{n \times r}$	Θ	Diagonal matrix of principal angles between subspaces	$\mathbb{R}^{r \times r}$
$w_k(\mu)$	Smooth weighting functions for local reduced bases, obtained via clustering	\mathbb{R}	\mathcal{D}_k	Subdomain of the parameter space \mathcal{D} used to define local reduced bases	$\subset \mathcal{D}$
V_k	Local reduced basis constructed from snapshots restricted to the subdomain \mathcal{D}_k	$\mathbb{R}^{n \times r_k}$	$\mathcal{S}(n, r)$	Schubert variety — structured submanifold of the Grassmann manifold representing rank- r subspaces with specific incidence properties	Manifold subset of $\mathcal{G}(n, r)$
I_M	Subspace interpolation map from the parameter domain to the tangent space of the reference subspace	$I_M : \mathcal{D} \rightarrow T[V_0]G(n, r)$	$\eta_k(\mu)$	Local error indicator for hierarchical POD	$\eta_k(\mu) \in \mathbb{R}$
r_{\min}	Minimum rank used when lifting or truncating local bases to a common dimension for interpolation	$r_{\min} \in \mathbb{N}$	r_{\max}	Maximum rank used when lifting or truncating local bases to a common dimension for interpolation	$r_{\max} \in \mathbb{N}$
$\mathcal{F}_H(\mu)$	High-fidelity model for parameter μ	\mathbb{R}^n	$\mathcal{F}_L(\mu)$	Low-fidelity (fast but approximate) model for parameter μ	\mathbb{R}^n
$\delta(\mu)$	Correction term representing the difference between high- and low-fidelity models	$\delta(\mu) \in \mathbb{R}^n$	V_L	Reduced basis obtained from snapshots of the low-fidelity model	$V_L \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times r}$
V_δ	Reduced basis obtained from high-fidelity corrections $\delta(\mu_j^H)$	$V_\delta \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times r_\delta}$	$\delta(\mu_j^H)$	High-fidelity correction evaluated at a specific high-fidelity training parameter μ_j^H	$\delta(\mu_j^H) \in \mathbb{R}^n$
S_α	Subdomain / substructure α	N/A	Ω_0	Reference finite-element mesh	Mesh nodes in \mathbb{R}^d
$\Omega(\mu)$	Deformed mesh corresponding to parameter μ	Mesh nodes in \mathbb{R}^d	x_0	Reference node in Ω_0	\mathbb{R}^d
x	Deformed position of node corresponding to x_0	\mathbb{R}^d	$\Psi(x_0, \mu)$	Mapping from reference mesh to deformed mesh	$\mathbb{R}^d \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^d$
V^0	Reference POD basis on Ω_0	$\mathbb{R}^{n \times r}$	$v_j(x, \mu)$	Transported POD mode defined on deformed mesh $\Omega(\mu)$	\mathbb{R}^n
$c_{i,\alpha}$	Coefficient of gPC expansion for reduced coordinate i	Scalar	$\Phi_\alpha(\mu)$	Multivariate polynomial basis function in gPC expansion	Scalar
p	Maximum polynomial degree in gPC expansion	\mathbb{N}	S	Online speed-up: ratio of full-order model runtime to reduced-order model runtime	Scalar
r	Dimension of the reduced basis (number of retained modes)	\mathbb{N}	t_{off}	Offline training / basis construction cost	Scalar (time)
t_{on}	Online query / evaluation cost	Scalar (time)	ϵ_x	Relative error in the state vector	Scalar
ϵ_y	Relative error in the quantity of interest	Scalar			

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Supplementary Material to: "From Snapshots to Manifolds: A Practical Roadmap For Interpolatory Reduced-Order Modeling"

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This document serves as supplementary material to "From Snapshots to Manifolds: A Practical Roadmap For Interpolatory Reduced-Order Modeling". This material includes a **Bibliometric Perspective** on the evolution of each interpolatory ROM category, as taxonomized in the original material, a **detailed overview of the proposed variations and expansions E1-E5** to the basic categories introduced in the paper, and a **library of ready to implement pseudo code algorithms**.

1. Bibliometric Perspectives

Figure 1. Bibliometric overview of interpolation-based ROM research (1975–2025). (a) Annual publication trends for each technique family T1–T7 and surveys, (b) Disciplinary composition of papers in each family.

Figure 1 surveys 12,221 Scopus-indexed journal and conference records (1975–2025) and reveals a three-stage evolution. During the formative phase (1975–1994) annual output was almost exclusively anchored in *T1: POD/Snapshot-based Projection* with early syntheses [1, 2]. Neither balanced-truncation nor Krylov ideas were yet computationally tractable, and interpolation appeared only as ad-hoc spline fits to POD coefficients. The expansion phase (1995–2012) shows an order-of-magnitude rise in publications and a rapid diversification of families of techniques. *T2: Transfer-Function and System-Matrix Interpolation* and *T4: Krylov / Interpolatory (Moment-Matching)* approaches gained prominence after the Padé and Lanczos generalizations [3], while in *T3: Gramian / Balanced-truncation* balanced-Gramian methods benefited from low-rank Lyapunov solvers [4]. *T5: Parameter-sampling and Reduced-basis* strategies matured through reduced-basis and sparse-grid algorithms [5, 6], and *T6: Structure-preserving, Passive and Second-order Techniques* Loewner framework variants emerged from the controls community [7]. In *T7: Manifold-based Interpolation of Reduced Bases*, Grassmann interpolation triggered the first wave of manifold papers [8] that are critically evaluated in [9, 10].

Since 2013 the field has stabilised at around 100 papers per year including a renewed surge of literature reviews [11, 12]. The sequence of seven pie charts in Figure 1 tracks the total distribution of the corpus across various disciplines. Engineering occupies the largest sector, typically 30–40% of all papers, highlighting that interpolation-based MOR is still driven chiefly by engineering applications such as aeroelasticity, acoustics, and thermo-fluid systems. Mathematics consistently supply the second-largest share, reflecting the fields analytical backbone in projection theory, balanced truncation, and manifold geometry. Computer-science, the third contributor, signals the influx of machine-learning-centric ROM, data assimilation, and digital-twin research.

2. METHODOLOGICAL VARIATIONS & EXTENSIONS

In the main part of this work, the seven foundational interpolation ROM paradigms T1-T7 were laid out. However, practical applications frequently demand further refinements to address computational constraints, data scarcity and noticeable geometric and structural variations. In this section, we present in detail the sequence of extensions E1-E5 along with how they build upon T1-7.

(a) E1: Hierarchical and Locally Refined POD

Figure 2. Comparison of classical POD (left) and hierarchical POD (right).

While classical POD uses a single SVD of the snapshot matrix \mathbf{S} to produce a global basis; hierarchical POD (HPOD) [13–15] first decomposes the parametric domain $\mathcal{D} = \bigcup \mathcal{D}_k$ as depicted in Figure 2 and performs an SVD for each part

$$\mathbf{S}_k = \mathbf{U}_k \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_k \mathbf{Z}_k, \quad \mathbf{V}_k = \mathbf{U}_k(:, 1:r_k). \quad (2.1)$$

The columns of every local basis \mathbf{V}_k are then joined into a new snapshot matrix and a second SVD produces a coarser basis \mathbf{V} . The process can be repeated if the error indicator

$$\eta_k(\mu) = \|\mathbf{u}(t, \mu) - \mathbf{V}_k \mathbf{u}(t, \mu)\|_2 \quad (2.2)$$

is larger than a chosen tolerance in any part of the domain. Every local basis may have a different dimension. To blend them smoothly one maps all local bases to $G(n, r_{\max})$, or $G(n, r_{\min})$, using a lift or truncate strategy [16, 17] and interpolates them using the logarithm and exponential constructions from T7: *Manifold-based Interpolation of Reduced Bases*. HPOD keeps the energy-optimal property of POD inside each part while keeping the dimension small in regions where the solution changes little. Its main weakness is that a mode which is important only in a later level can be lost during the earlier SVDs unless the indicator η_k is chosen with care.

(b) E2: Multi-Fidelity Reduction with Adaptive Sampling

Assume a fast but rough model \mathcal{F}_L (*L-low fidelity*) that produces the state vectors $\mathbf{u}^L(t, \mu)$ and a slow but accurate model \mathcal{F}_H (*H-high fidelity*) that produces the state vectors $\mathbf{u}^H(t, \mu)$ for the same physical problem. In a two-level reduced model, one can generate two reduced basis, a low fidelity basis $\mathbf{V}_L \in \mathbb{R}^{n_L \times r_L}$ obtained from many low fidelity snapshots, and a correction basis $\mathbf{V}_\delta \in \mathbb{R}^{n_H \times r_\delta}$ obtained from a small amount of high fidelity correction snapshots.

At each high fidelity training parameter μ_*^H , a correction snapshot is defined as,

$$\delta(\mu_j^H) = \mathbf{u}^H(t, \mu_j^H) - \Pi_{L \rightarrow H}(\mathbf{u}^L(t, \mu_j^H)), \quad (2.3)$$

where $\Pi_{L \rightarrow H}$ is a lifting operator that maps the low fidelity to the high fidelity space.

A two level reduced model, often also called a Response Surface Method, then approximates the high fidelity state as

$$\mathbf{u}^H(t, \mu) \approx \underbrace{\Pi_{L \rightarrow H}(\mathbf{V}_L \hat{\mathbf{u}}^L(t, \mu))}_{\text{LF prediction lifted to HF space}} + \underbrace{\mathbf{V}_\delta \hat{\mathbf{u}}^\delta(t, \mu)}_{\text{HF correction}} \quad (2.4)$$

where \mathbf{V}_L is obtained from many low-fidelity (LF) snapshots and \mathbf{V}_δ is obtained from a small number of high-fidelity (HF) corrections $\delta(\mu_j^H)$ [18, 19]. New HF points are chosen in the regions in the parametric space where an error estimator, for example the variance of a Gaussian-process fit or a reduced-basis residual, is largest [20–22]. The idea enlarges the *parameter-sampling* family of *T5: Parameter-sampling and Reduced-basis* by letting most snapshots come from the cheap model while using the expensive model only in the parameter regions where it matters. This has been useful for example in design optimisation for aerodynamics [23, 24] and in climate prediction [25]. Its accuracy is limited by how well \mathcal{F}_L represents the true physics in parameter values where no HF data have yet been taken. This is illustrated in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Multi-fidelity model reduction with adaptive sampling: (a) low-fidelity (LF) and high-fidelity (HF) discretizations of the same geometry; (b) surrogate fit comparisons.

A related approach projects the full matrices at a few training points, that is

$$\hat{\mathbf{A}}(\mu_i) = \mathbf{V}(\mu_i)^\top \mathbf{A}(\mu_i) \mathbf{V}(\mu_i), \quad (2.5)$$

and then interpolates the small matrices $\hat{\mathbf{A}}(\mu_i)$ to obtain $\tilde{\mathbf{A}}(\mu_*)$ at new parameters [26]. Before interpolation each local matrix is rotated into a common frame by an orthogonal transformation in a manner similar to *T2: Transfer-Function and System-Matrix Interpolation-T3: Gramian / Balanced-truncation*, so that matrix entries refer to the same physical directions [27]. The result is evaluated in micro-seconds and is therefore attractive for Monte-Carlo loops [28–31]. However, extra algebra is needed to guarantee stability or passivity of the interpolated matrix.

(c) E3: Component-Mode Synthesis Sub-structuring and Matrix Interpolation

The Craig-Bampton approach, or Component-mode synthesis (CMS) with sub-structuring, divides a complex structure into subdomains $\{S_\alpha\}$ as shown in Figure 4 and condenses each part before global coupling [33]. For a single component the physical displacement vector is written

Figure 4. Craig–Bampton (component-mode) condensation of a bolted beam assembly. Each substructure Ω_α is discretised independently, its interior fixed-interface modes \mathbf{V}_α^i (blue) are retained, and its static constraint modes \mathbf{C}_α enforce compatibility along the purple interface mesh. Adapted from [32].

$$\mathbf{q}_\alpha = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{q}_\alpha^i \\ \mathbf{q}_\alpha^b \\ \mathbf{q}_\alpha \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{q}_\alpha \in \mathbb{R}^{n_\alpha}, \mathbf{q}_\alpha^i \in \mathbb{R}^{n_\alpha^i}, \mathbf{q}_\alpha^b \in \mathbb{R}^{n_\alpha^b}, \quad (2.6)$$

where q_α^i are the internal DOFs, q_α^b are the boundary DOFs and $n_\alpha = n_\alpha^i + n_\alpha^b$. The mass and stiffness can be accordingly partitioned as

$$\mathbf{K}_\alpha = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{K}_{ii} & \mathbf{K}_{ib} \\ \mathbf{K}_{bi} & \mathbf{K}_{bb} \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{M}_\alpha = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{M}_{ii} & 0 \\ 0 & \mathbf{M}_{bb} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (2.7)$$

where the mass matrix is typically used in lumped form. The equation of motion for the substructure is

$$\mathbf{M}_\alpha \ddot{\mathbf{q}}_\alpha + \mathbf{K}_\alpha \mathbf{q}_\alpha = \mathbf{f}_\alpha(t). \quad (2.8)$$

Then the interior eigenvalue problem can be solved, with the boundary DOFs fixed: $\mathbf{K}_{ii} \mathbf{v}_j = \lambda_j \mathbf{M}_{ii} \mathbf{v}_j$, $j = 1, \dots, r_\alpha$ and an amount of r_α modes are kept in order to satisfy a predefined accuracy. These are stored in the fixed interface vibration modes $\mathbf{V}_\alpha^i \in \mathbb{R}^{n_\alpha^i \times r_\alpha}$, while the static constraint modes $\mathbf{C}_\alpha^i \in \mathbb{R}^{n_\alpha^i \times n_\alpha^b}$ computed by solving $\mathbf{K}_{ii} \mathbf{C}_\alpha^i = -\mathbf{K}_{ib}$. The full transformation for the substructure then reads as

$$\mathbf{q}_\alpha = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{V}_\alpha^i & \mathbf{C}_\alpha^i \\ 0 & \mathbf{I} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \hat{\mathbf{q}}_\alpha^i \\ \hat{\mathbf{q}}_\alpha^b \end{bmatrix} \equiv \mathbf{T}_\alpha \begin{bmatrix} \hat{\mathbf{q}}_\alpha^i \\ \hat{\mathbf{q}}_\alpha^b \end{bmatrix}. \quad (2.9)$$

Substituting $\mathbf{q}_\alpha = \mathbf{T}_\alpha \hat{\mathbf{q}}_\alpha$ into Equation (2.8) and pre-multiplying by \mathbf{T}_α^\top yields the reduced substructure equation.

$$\hat{\mathbf{M}}_\alpha \ddot{\hat{\mathbf{q}}}_\alpha + \hat{\mathbf{K}}_\alpha \hat{\mathbf{q}}_\alpha = \hat{\mathbf{f}}_\alpha(t), \quad \hat{\mathbf{M}}_\alpha = \mathbf{T}_\alpha^\top \mathbf{M}_\alpha \mathbf{T}_\alpha, \quad \hat{\mathbf{K}}_\alpha = \mathbf{T}_\alpha^\top \mathbf{K}_\alpha \mathbf{T}_\alpha, \quad \hat{\mathbf{f}}_\alpha(t) = \mathbf{T}_\alpha^\top \mathbf{f}_\alpha. \quad (2.10)$$

The Galerkin projection using \mathbf{T}_α as a reduced basis yields the reduced mass and stiffness operators $\hat{\mathbf{M}}_\alpha(\mu), \hat{\mathbf{K}}_\alpha(\mu) \in \mathbb{R}^{(r_\alpha + n_\alpha^b) \times (r_\alpha + n_\alpha^b)}$, the order of which is independent of the underlying finite-element resolution.

When material properties or geometry vary with a parameter μ , regenerating these operators at each query would defeat the purpose of reduction. Instead, one pre-computes the matrices at

training points $\{\mu_i\}$ and interpolates entry-wise, that is

$$\hat{\mathbf{K}}_{\alpha}(\mu_*) = \sum_i \varphi_i(\mu_*) \hat{\mathbf{K}}_{\alpha}(\mu_i), \quad \hat{\mathbf{M}}_{\alpha}(\mu_*) = \sum_i \varphi_i(\mu_*) \hat{\mathbf{M}}_{\alpha}(\mu_i), \quad (2.11)$$

using barycentric or inverse-distance weights φ_i [34]. The condensed subcomponents are then re-assembled to form the global Craig–Bampton system, which naturally preserves the second-order mechanical structure discussed in *T6: Structure-preserving, Passive and Second-order Techniques*. Because substructures are handled independently, libraries of parametric components accelerate studies of damaged assemblies or modular designs [35, 36]. Interface compatibility (i.e. ensuring that the interface DOFs and substructures remain consistent so that the reduced subcomponents can be correctly interpolated at any μ_*) across parameters is crucial. An effective remedy to maintain interface compatibility is the dynamic updating of constraint modes [37]. This approach can be combined with the Schubert-variety lifting strategy of Family T7 to accommodate rank changes without sacrificing continuity.

(d) E4: Shape Maps and Mesh Morphing

Figure 5. Radial–basis–function morphing of an aircraft wing surface.

Geometry-dependent problems demand that both the governing operators and the trial space evolve with the shape. Let Ω_0 be a reference finite-element mesh and let $\Psi(\mathbf{x}_0, \mu) : \Omega_0 \rightarrow \Omega(\mu)$ map every reference node \mathbf{x}_0 to its deformed position \mathbf{x} for the parameter value μ , as depicted in Figure 5 [38]. Popular choices for Ψ include radial-basis functions, free-form deformation and elasticity solutions. All these options deliver sparse, easily invertible mappings. Given a reference POD basis $\mathbf{V}^0 = [\mathbf{v}_1^0, \dots, \mathbf{v}_r^0]$ on Ω_0 , the transported field

$$\mathbf{v}_j(\mathbf{x}, \mu) = \mathbf{v}_j^0(\Psi^{-1}(\mathbf{x}, \mu)), \quad j = 1, \dots, r, \quad (2.12)$$

is well defined on the deformed mesh $\Omega(\mu)$. Because transport disrupts orthogonality, a thin QR re-orthonormalises the columns, producing $\mathbf{V}(\mu)$ that can be used directly in the Galerkin projection formulas of *T1: POD/Snapshot-based Projection*. For small shape variations, enriching \mathbf{V}^0 with analytical shape-sensitivities $\partial \mathbf{u} / \partial \mu$ tightens accuracy without increasing the transported rank [39].

The approach is compatible with all interpolation families: *T2: Transfer-Function and System-Matrix Interpolation* exploits the fixed reduced dimension; balanced truncation (T3) benefits from shape-consistent Gramians; and manifold techniques (T7) further refine $\mathbf{V}(\mu)$ by geodesic averaging when several design points share a common map. Its main limitation is the occurrence of mesh entanglement for large deformations. This is mitigated by adaptive remeshing, high-order mapping or incremental morphing strategies that partition a large shape change into admissible sub-steps [40, 41]. When paired with the Schubert-variety lifting introduced in *T7: Manifold-based Interpolation of Reduced Bases*, the method gains the ability to accommodate rank changes triggered by topology modifications or local refinements. This enhancement significantly extends its applicability to complex, highly nonlinear design spaces.

(e) E5: Spectral Expansions, DEIM, and Hyper-Reduction

For many parametric problems, the reduced coordinates obtained from snapshot-POD vary smoothly with the parameters, allowing a generalized polynomial-chaos (gPC) surrogate of the form

$$\hat{\mathbf{u}}_i(\mu_\star) \approx \sum_{|\alpha| \leq p} c_{i,\alpha} \Phi_\alpha(\mu_\star) \quad (2.13)$$

to achieve spectral convergence whenever $\mu \mapsto \hat{\mathbf{u}}_i(\mu)$ is analytic and the parameter dimension d is moderate [42, 43]. The coefficients $c_{i,\alpha}$ are computed using either projection or least-squares regression on the snapshot ensemble [44, 45]. A recent refinement introduces a DEIM-based collocation stage, which selects an optimally conditioned set of interpolation nodes. This addition improves numerical stability and reduces the offline computational cost [46]. To capture multilinear interactions in higher-dimensional parameter spaces, tensor decompositions such as CANDECOMP/PARAFAC have been employed to reduce storage and evaluation cost in high dimensional gPC expansions [47, 48]. When smoothness deteriorates, hybrid approaches often revert locally to radial-basis or spline interpolation methods [49]. Nevertheless, the exponential growth in the number of gPC terms, given by $\binom{p+d}{d}$, remains a significant limiting factor. Sparse-gPC and adaptive selection techniques reduce the number of non-zero $c_{i,\alpha}$ coefficients, and as a result help to reduce this cost, but remain a partial solution to the problem [50, 51].

Even when a gPC expansion is available, the cost of evaluating the full-dimension residual $\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{V}\hat{\mathbf{u}}, \mu)$ can dominate the online runtime. Both DEIM and hyper-reduction overcome this bottleneck by first collecting residual snapshots (and, if necessary, their Jacobians), then constructing a collateral POD basis \mathbf{U}_m , selecting a small set of sample indices or elements of size $m \ll n$, and finally reconstructing the full residual from those samples. Algebraically, DEIM employs a Boolean sampling matrix $\mathbf{P} \in \{0, 1\}^{n \times m}$, leading to the approximation

$$f(\mathbf{V}\hat{\mathbf{u}}, \mu) \approx \mathbf{U}(\mathbf{P}^T \mathbf{U})^{-1} \mathbf{P}^T f(\mathbf{V}\hat{\mathbf{u}}, \mu). \quad (2.14)$$

Hyper-reduction schemes, such as empirical cubature, instead approximate the integral (variational, weak) form of the PDE over the domain Ω by a reduced quadrature restricted to a subset Ω_Z . This subset is selected using a Boolean selector \mathbf{Z} , which targets specific finite-element entities [52, 53]. In both cases, the online complexity is reduced to $\mathcal{O}(m)$ and the sparsity pattern of the original assembly is preserved.

Figure 6. Schematic of the four-stage DEIM/hyper-reduction pipeline.

In modern workflows, spectral surrogates and nonlinear-reduction techniques are deeply intertwined: DEIM-assisted gPC regression computes the reduced coordinates, hyper-reduction accelerates the resulting residual evaluations, and these approximations are further combined with operator-interpolation or manifold-averaging strategies from Families T1–T7. Residual-based error indicators and incremental SVD updates ensure that both the polynomial basis and the sampling operators \mathbf{P} and \mathbf{Z} remain up to date, with Grassmann log–exp maps refreshing sampling matrices without full re-factorizations. The resulting ROMs thus maintain high accuracy over extended transients while satisfying stringent runtime requirements.

3. Detailed Algorithms for T1–T7

Algorithm 1 T1: *POD/Snapshot-based Projection (Family T1)*

Input: • Snapshot generator $\mathbf{u}(t, \mu)$ for $t \in [0, T]$ and $\mu \in \mathcal{D}$

- Index sets $\{t_i\}_{i=1}^{N_t}, \{\mu_j\}_{j=1}^M$; total $N = N_t M$ snapshots
- Energy tolerance $0 < \varepsilon \ll 1$
- State matrix $\mathbf{M}(\mu) \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ (SPD) and right-hand side $\mathbf{f} : \mathbb{R}^n \times \mathcal{D} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$

Output: Trial basis \mathbf{V} , test basis \mathbf{W} , reduced matrix $\hat{\mathbf{M}}$, and reduced vector field $\hat{\mathbf{f}}$

- 1: **Assemble snapshot matrix:** $\mathbf{S} = [\mathbf{u}(t_i, \mu_j)]_{i,j} \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times N}$
- 2: **Compute economy SVD:** $\mathbf{S} = \mathbf{U}\mathbf{\Sigma}\mathbf{W}^\top$ with singular values $\sigma_1 \geq \dots \geq \sigma_N$
- 3: **Select reduced dimension r :**

$$r = \min \left\{ k : \frac{\sum_{m=1}^k \sigma_m^2}{\sum_{m=1}^N \sigma_m^2} \geq 1 - \varepsilon \right\}, \quad 1 \leq r \leq N \quad (\text{B.1})$$

- 4: **Define trial basis:** $\mathbf{V} = \mathbf{U}(:, 1:r)$
- 5: **if** Petrov–Galerkin variant required **then**
- 6: Compute test basis $\mathbf{W} \leftarrow \arg \min_{\mathbf{W} \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times r}} \|\mathbf{W}^\top \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{V}_r \hat{\mathbf{u}}, \mu)\|_2$ ▷ e.g. $\mathbf{W} = \mathbf{M}\mathbf{V}$ or least-squares residual basis
- 7: **else**
- 8: $\mathbf{W} \leftarrow \mathbf{V}$ ▷ Galerkin choice
- 9: **end if**
- 10: **Assemble reduced operators:**

$$\hat{\mathbf{M}}(\mu) = \mathbf{W}^\top \mathbf{M}(\mu) \mathbf{V}, \quad \hat{\mathbf{f}}(\hat{\mathbf{u}}, \mu) = \mathbf{W}^\top \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{V}_r \hat{\mathbf{u}}, \mu) \quad (\text{B.2})$$

- 11: **Solve reduced system:** $\hat{\mathbf{M}}(\mu) \dot{\hat{\mathbf{u}}}(t, \mu) = \hat{\mathbf{f}}(\hat{\mathbf{u}}(t, \mu), \mu)$, with appropriate reduced initial data
 - 12: **return** $(\mathbf{V}, \mathbf{W}, \hat{\mathbf{M}}, \hat{\mathbf{f}})$
-

Algorithm 2 Transfer-Function & System-Matrix Interpolation (Family T2)

Input: Training parameters $\{\mu_i\}_{i=0}^M$, reduced dimension r , interpolation basis $\{\varphi_i(\cdot)\}$ with $\sum_{i=0}^M \varphi_i(\mu) = 1$, and (optionally) frequency-response data $\{\mathbf{H}(j\omega_k, \mu_i)\}$

Output: Common trial basis \mathbf{V}_0 and interpolated reduced operators $(\tilde{\mathbf{A}}(\mu), \tilde{\mathbf{B}}(\mu), \tilde{\mathbf{C}}(\mu), \tilde{\mathbf{D}}(\mu))$

Offline stage (intrusive projection)

- 1: **for** $i = 0, \dots, M$ **do**
- 2: Form snapshot matrix $\mathbf{S}_i = [\mathbf{u}(t_m, \mu_i)]_{m=1}^{N_i}$
- 3: Compute POD basis $\mathbf{V}_i \leftarrow \text{SVD}_r(\mathbf{S}_i)$ $\triangleright \mathbf{V}_i \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times r}$
- 4: Project full operators to obtain $(\hat{\mathbf{A}}_i, \hat{\mathbf{B}}_i, \hat{\mathbf{C}}_i, \hat{\mathbf{D}}_i)$
 $\hat{\mathbf{A}}_i = \mathbf{V}_i^\top \mathbf{A}(\mu_i) \mathbf{V}_i$, $\hat{\mathbf{B}}_i = \mathbf{V}_i^\top \mathbf{B}(\mu_i)$, $\hat{\mathbf{C}}_i = \mathbf{C}(\mu_i) \mathbf{V}_i$
- 5: **end for**
- Alignment to reference basis** \mathbf{V}_0
- 6: **for** $i = 1, \dots, M$ **do**
- 7: Compute thin SVD $\mathbf{V}_0^\top \mathbf{V}_i = \mathbf{U}_i \mathbf{\Xi}_i \mathbf{W}_i^\top$
- 8: Solve Procrustes problem $\mathbf{Q}_i \leftarrow \mathbf{U}_i \mathbf{W}_i^\top$ $\triangleright \mathbf{Q}_i \in \text{SO}(r)$
- 9: Congruence-transform operators

$$\tilde{\mathbf{A}}_i = \mathbf{Q}_i^\top \hat{\mathbf{A}}_i \mathbf{Q}_i, \quad \tilde{\mathbf{B}}_i = \mathbf{Q}_i^\top \hat{\mathbf{B}}_i, \quad \tilde{\mathbf{C}}_i = \hat{\mathbf{C}}_i \mathbf{Q}_i, \quad \tilde{\mathbf{D}}_i = \hat{\mathbf{D}}_i \quad (\text{B.3})$$

10: **end for**

Optional non-intrusive variant (Loewner pencil)

- 11: **if** only frequency responses are available **then**
- 12: **for** $i = 0, \dots, M$ **do**
- 13: Assemble Loewner matrices $\mathbf{L}_i, \mathbf{L}_{\sigma,i}$ from data
- 14: Solve pencil $(\mathbf{L}_{\sigma,i} - \lambda \mathbf{L}_i) \mathbf{v} = 0$, extract $(\hat{\mathbf{A}}_i, \hat{\mathbf{B}}_i, \hat{\mathbf{C}}_i)$
- 15: **end for**
- 16: Apply Steps 6–8 to align $\hat{\mathbf{A}}_i, \hat{\mathbf{B}}_i, \hat{\mathbf{C}}_i$
- 17: **end if**

Online stage (query parameter μ_*)

- 18: Evaluate weights $\{\varphi_i(\mu_*)\}$ (e.g. cubic B-splines)
- 19: Interpolate reduced operators

$$\tilde{\mathbf{A}}(\mu_*) = \sum_{i=0}^M \varphi_i(\mu_*) \tilde{\mathbf{A}}_i, \quad \tilde{\mathbf{B}}(\mu_*) = \sum_{i=0}^M \varphi_i(\mu_*) \tilde{\mathbf{B}}_i, \quad (\text{B.4})$$

$$\tilde{\mathbf{C}}(\mu_*) = \sum_{i=0}^M \varphi_i(\mu_*) \tilde{\mathbf{C}}_i, \quad \tilde{\mathbf{D}}(\mu_*) = \sum_{i=0}^M \varphi_i(\mu_*) \tilde{\mathbf{D}}_i \quad (\text{B.5})$$

- 20: **return** ROM $(\mathbf{V}_0, \tilde{\mathbf{A}}(\mu_*), \tilde{\mathbf{B}}(\mu_*), \tilde{\mathbf{C}}(\mu_*), \tilde{\mathbf{D}}(\mu_*))$ $\triangleright O(r^2)$ online cost

Algorithm 3 Balanced Truncation with Low-Rank ADI and Operator Interpolation (Family T3)

Input: Training parameters $\{\mu_i\}_{i=0}^M$, target order r , ADI shifts $\{\gamma_j\}_{j=1}^\ell$, interpolation weights $\{\varphi_i(\cdot)\}$ with $\sum_i \varphi_i(\mu) = 1$

Output: Interpolated reduced quadruple $(\widehat{\mathbf{A}}(\mu), \widehat{\mathbf{B}}(\mu), \widehat{\mathbf{C}}(\mu), \widehat{\mathbf{D}}(\mu))$

Offline stage – balanced reductions at training points

- 1: **for** $i = 0, \dots, M$ **do**
- 2: Solve controllability Lyapunov with low-rank ADI to obtain $\mathbf{Z}_i \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times \ell}$
- 3: Solve observability Lyapunov similarly to obtain \mathbf{Y}_i
- 4: Compute balancing SVD $\mathbf{Z}_i^\top \mathbf{Y}_i = \mathbf{U}_i \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_i \mathbf{V}_i^\top$
- 5: Form similarity transform $\mathbf{T}_i = \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_i^{-1/2} \mathbf{U}_i^\top \mathbf{Z}_i^\top$
- 6: Extract reduced operators (retain first r balanced states):

$$\mathbf{A}_{r,i} = \mathbf{T}_i \mathbf{A}_i \mathbf{T}_i^{-1}(1:r, 1:r), \quad \mathbf{B}_{r,i} = \mathbf{T}_i \mathbf{B}_i(1:r, :), \quad (\text{B.6})$$

$$\mathbf{C}_{r,i} = \mathbf{C}_i \mathbf{T}_i^{-1}(:, 1:r), \quad \mathbf{D}_{r,i} = \mathbf{D}_i \quad (\text{B.7})$$

- 7: **end for**
- 8: Store $\{\mathbf{A}_{r,i}, \mathbf{B}_{r,i}, \mathbf{C}_{r,i}, \mathbf{D}_{r,i}\}$

Optional alignment (compact subspace mapping)

- 9: Choose reference index $i=0$
- 10: **for** $i = 1, \dots, M$ **do**
- 11: Compute skew-symmetric generator $\boldsymbol{\Xi}_i = \text{Log}(\mathbf{C}_{r,0}^\top \mathbf{C}_{r,i})$
- 12: Form alignment matrix $\mathbf{R}_i = \exp(-\frac{1}{2} \boldsymbol{\Xi}_i)$
- 13: Rotate reduced operators:

$$\widetilde{\mathbf{A}}_{r,i} = \mathbf{R}_i^\top \mathbf{A}_{r,i} \mathbf{R}_i, \quad \widetilde{\mathbf{B}}_{r,i} = \mathbf{R}_i^\top \mathbf{B}_{r,i}, \quad (\text{B.8})$$

$$\widetilde{\mathbf{C}}_{r,i} = \mathbf{C}_{r,i} \mathbf{R}_i, \quad \widetilde{\mathbf{D}}_{r,i} = \mathbf{D}_{r,i} \quad (\text{B.9})$$

- 14: **end for**
- 15: Replace stored sets by $\{\widetilde{\mathbf{A}}_{r,i}, \widetilde{\mathbf{B}}_{r,i}, \widetilde{\mathbf{C}}_{r,i}, \widetilde{\mathbf{D}}_{r,i}\}$

Online stage – query parameter μ_*

- 16: Evaluate weights $\{\varphi_i(\mu_*)\}$
- 17: Interpolate component-wise

$$\widehat{\mathbf{A}}(\mu_*) = \sum_{i=0}^M \varphi_i(\mu_*) \widetilde{\mathbf{A}}_{r,i}, \quad \widehat{\mathbf{B}}(\mu_*) = \sum_{i=0}^M \varphi_i(\mu_*) \widetilde{\mathbf{B}}_{r,i}, \quad (\text{B.10})$$

$$\widehat{\mathbf{C}}(\mu_*) = \sum_{i=0}^M \varphi_i(\mu_*) \widetilde{\mathbf{C}}_{r,i}, \quad \widehat{\mathbf{D}}(\mu_*) = \sum_{i=0}^M \varphi_i(\mu_*) \widetilde{\mathbf{D}}_{r,i} \quad (\text{B.11})$$

- 18: **return** $(\widehat{\mathbf{A}}(\mu_*), \widehat{\mathbf{B}}(\mu_*), \widehat{\mathbf{C}}(\mu_*), \widehat{\mathbf{D}}(\mu_*))$ $\triangleright O(r^2)$ online cost; no full-order solves

Algorithm 4 Tangential Krylov-IRKA Moment-Matching (Family T4)

Input: Full-order system matrices $\mathbf{A}(\mu)$, $\mathbf{B}(\mu)$, $\mathbf{C}(\mu)$; initial interpolation points $\{s_\ell^{(0)}\}_{\ell=1}^m$; initial right tangential directions $\{\mathbf{r}_\ell^{(0)}\}$; initial left tangential directions $\{\mathbf{l}_\ell^{(0)}\}$; convergence tolerance $\varepsilon_{\text{IRKA}}$

Output: Reduced-order matrices $\widehat{\mathbf{A}}$, $\widehat{\mathbf{B}}$, $\widehat{\mathbf{C}}$ that satisfy the first-order \mathcal{H}_2 -optimality conditions

1: $k \leftarrow 0$

2: **repeat**

Step 1: Build trial and test subspaces

3: **for** $\ell = 1, \dots, m$ **do**

4: Solve $(\mathbf{A} - s_\ell^{(k)}\mathbf{I})\mathbf{v}_\ell = \mathbf{B}\mathbf{r}_\ell^{(k)}$

5: Solve $(\mathbf{A}^\top - \overline{s}_\ell^{(k)}\mathbf{I})\mathbf{w}_\ell = \mathbf{C}^\top \mathbf{l}_\ell^{(k)}$

6: **end for**

7: $\mathbf{V} \leftarrow \text{orth}[\mathbf{v}_1, \dots, \mathbf{v}_m]$

8: $\mathbf{W} \leftarrow \text{orth}[\mathbf{w}_1, \dots, \mathbf{w}_m]$

Step 2: Petrov–Galerkin projection

$$\widehat{\mathbf{A}} = \mathbf{W}^\top \mathbf{A} \mathbf{V}, \quad \widehat{\mathbf{B}} = \mathbf{W}^\top \mathbf{B}, \quad \widehat{\mathbf{C}} = \mathbf{C} \mathbf{V} \quad (\text{B.12})$$

Step 3: Update shifts and directions

9: Compute eigenpairs $\widehat{\mathbf{A}} \mathbf{z}_\ell = \hat{\lambda}_\ell \mathbf{z}_\ell$

10: **for** $\ell = 1, \dots, m$ **do**

11: $s_\ell^{(k+1)} \leftarrow -\hat{\lambda}_\ell$

12: $\mathbf{r}_\ell^{(k+1)} \leftarrow \widehat{\mathbf{C}} \mathbf{z}_\ell$

13: $\mathbf{l}_\ell^{(k+1)\top} \leftarrow \mathbf{z}_\ell^\top \widehat{\mathbf{B}}$

14: **end for**

15: $k \leftarrow k + 1$

16: **until** $\max_\ell |s_\ell^{(k)} - s_\ell^{(k-1)}| \leq \varepsilon_{\text{IRKA}}$

17: **return** $\widehat{\mathbf{A}}$, $\widehat{\mathbf{B}}$, $\widehat{\mathbf{C}}$

Algorithm 5 Greedy Reduced-Basis with Residual Error Certification (Family T5)

Input: Training set $\Xi_{\text{train}} = \{\mu_i\}_{i=1}^{N_{\Xi}}$, affine decomposition $\mathbf{A}(\mu) = \sum_{q=1}^Q \theta_q(\mu) \mathbf{A}_q$, tolerance ε_{RB} , (optional) nonlinear term \mathbf{f} handled by EIM/DEIM

Output: Trial basis \mathbf{V}_r , reduced operators $\{\hat{\mathbf{A}}_q\}_{q=1}^Q$, error-bound ingredients for online evaluation

Offline stage

- 1: **if** non-affine or nonlinear terms present **then**
 - 2: Construct collateral basis \mathbf{U}_m and sampling matrix $\mathbf{P} \in \{0, 1\}^{n \times m}$ via EIM/DEIM
 - 3: **end if**
 - 4: Select initial parameter $\mu^{(1)}$ (e.g. random or max-residual seed)
 - 5: Collect full snapshot $\mathbf{u}^{(1)} = \mathbf{u}(\mu^{(1)})$; set $\mathbf{V}_1 = \text{orth}[\mathbf{u}^{(1)}]$, $r \leftarrow 1$
 - 6: **repeat**
 - 7: **for all** $\mu \in \Xi_{\text{train}}$ **do**
 - 8: Assemble reduced matrix $\hat{\mathbf{A}}(\mu) = \sum_{q=1}^Q \theta_q(\mu) \hat{\mathbf{A}}_q$ with $\hat{\mathbf{A}}_q = \mathbf{V}^{\top} \mathbf{A}_q \mathbf{V}$
 - 9: Solve reduced system for $\hat{\mathbf{u}}(\mu)$
 - 10: Evaluate residual bound $\Delta(\mu)$ using pre-computed coercivity lower bound $\alpha_{\text{LB}}(\mu)$
 - 11: **end for**
 - 12: $\mu_* \leftarrow \arg \max_{\mu \in \Xi_{\text{train}}} \Delta_r(\mu)$
 - 13: **if** $\Delta(\mu_*) \leq \varepsilon_{\text{RB}}$ **then**
 - 14: **break** ▷ stopping criterion satisfied
 - 15: **end if**
 - 16: Compute high-fidelity snapshot $\mathbf{u}_* = \mathbf{u}(\mu_*)$
 - 17: Augment basis $\mathbf{V} = \text{orth}[\mathbf{V}, \mathbf{u}_*]$, $r \leftarrow r + 1$
 - 18: **until** convergence
 - Online stage (query μ_*)**
 - 19: Assemble $\hat{\mathbf{A}}(\mu_*)$ and reduced right-hand side using affine coefficients $\theta_q(\mu_*)$
 - 20: **if** EIM/DEIM used **then**
 - 21: Evaluate nonlinear term at m indices ($\mathbf{P}^{\top} \mathbf{f}$), reconstruct via collateral basis
 - 22: **end if**
 - 23: Solve $\hat{\mathbf{A}}(\mu_*) \hat{\mathbf{u}}(\mu_*) = \hat{\mathbf{b}}(\mu_*)$
 - 24: (Optional) return error estimator $\Delta(\mu_*)$
 - 25: **return** $\hat{\mathbf{u}}(\mu_*), \Delta(\mu_*)$
-

Algorithm 7 Grassmann Interpolation with Inverse-Distance Weighting (Family T7)

Input: Support subspaces $[\mathbf{V}_j]_{j=1}^{N_{\text{sup}}} \subset G(n, r_j)$ at parameters $\{\boldsymbol{\mu}_j\}$; query parameter $\boldsymbol{\mu}_*$; inverse-distance exponent q ; gradient-refinement tolerance ε_G

Output: Interpolated orthonormal basis \mathbf{V}_* for $\mathcal{V}_* \approx \mathcal{V}(\boldsymbol{\mu}_*)$

Offline preparation (once)

- 1: **for** $j = 1, \dots, N_{\text{sup}}$ **do**
- 2: Thin QR: $\mathbf{V}_j = \mathbf{Q}_j \mathbf{R}_j$ ($\mathbf{Q}_j \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times r_j}$)
- 3: **end for**

Online stage for $\boldsymbol{\mu}_*$

- 4: (1) *Inverse-distance weights*: $d_j = \|\boldsymbol{\mu}_j - \boldsymbol{\mu}_*\|_2^q$, $\beta_j = d_j^{-1} / \sum_k d_k^{-1}$
- 5: (2) *Rank alignment*: choose strategy *truncate*: $r = \min_j r_j$, $\tilde{\mathbf{Q}}_j = \mathbf{Q}_j(:, 1:r)$;
lift: $r = \max_j r_j$, augment \mathbf{Q}_j with
 $r - r_j$ orthonormal columns to obtain $\tilde{\mathbf{Q}}_j \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times r}$
- 6: (3) *Mapping to a common tangent space*: reference $\tilde{\mathbf{Q}}_1$; for each j

$$\mathbf{Z}_j = (\mathbf{I} - \tilde{\mathbf{Q}}_1 \tilde{\mathbf{Q}}_1^\top) \tilde{\mathbf{Q}}_j (\tilde{\mathbf{Q}}_1^\top \tilde{\mathbf{Q}}_j)^{-1}, \quad \mathbf{Z}_j = \mathbf{U}_j \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_j \mathbf{W}_j^\top, \quad \mathbf{T}_j = \mathbf{U}_j \arctan(\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_j) \mathbf{W}_j^\top \quad (\text{B.14})$$

- 7: (4) *Barycentric average in the tangent space*: $\mathbf{T}_* = \sum_{j=1}^{N_{\text{sup}}} \beta_j \mathbf{T}_j$
- 8: (5) *Retraction to $G(n, r)$* : $\mathbf{U} \boldsymbol{\Theta} \mathbf{W}^\top = \text{svd}(\mathbf{T}_*)$, $\mathbf{V}_* = \tilde{\mathbf{Q}}_1 \mathbf{W} \cos \boldsymbol{\Theta} + \mathbf{U} \sin \boldsymbol{\Theta}$

Optional refinement

- 9: **while** $\|\nabla F_{\boldsymbol{\mu}_*}([\mathbf{V}_*])\|_F > \varepsilon_G$ **do**
- 10: $\mathbf{V}_* \leftarrow \text{Exp}_{\mathbf{V}_*}(-\nabla F_{\boldsymbol{\mu}_*}([\mathbf{V}_*]))$
- 11: **end while**
- 12: **return** \mathbf{V}_*

4. Nomenclature

Table 1: List of abbreviations.

Abbrev.	Meaning	Abbrev.	Meaning
AD	Automatic Differentiation	AF	Adaptive Filtering
ADI	Alternating Direction Implicit	ANN	Artificial Neural Network
API	Application Programming Interface	BIRKA	Balanced Iterative Reduced-Krylov Algorithm
BT	Balanced Truncation	CAE	Convolution Autoencoder
CANDECOM	Canonical Decomposition (tensor factorization)	CFD	Computational Fluid Dynamics
CNN	Convolutional Neural Network	CMS	Component Mode Synthesis
CPU	Central Processing Unit	DEIM	Discrete Empirical Interpolation Method
DMD	Dynamic Mode Decomposition	DL	Deep Learning
DOF	Degree of Freedom	EIM	Empirical Interpolation Method
ECSW	Energy Conserving Sampling and Weighting	EnKF	Ensemble Kalman Filter
FD	Finite Difference	FEA	Finite Element Analysis
FH	High-Fidelity Model	FL	Low-Fidelity Model
FNO	Fourier Neural Operator	FSI	Fluid-Structure Interaction
GAN	Generative Adversarial Network	Gpc	Generalized Polynomial Chaos

Abbrev.	Meaning	Abbrev.	Meaning
GPG	Global POD Galerkin	GPOD	Global Proper Orthogonal Decomposition
GPR	Gaussian Process Regression	GPU	Graphics Processing Unit
HF	High Fidelity	HPC	High Performance Computing
HPOD	Hierarchical Proper Orthogonal Decomposition	I/O	Input/Output
IRKA	Iterative Rational Krylov Algorithm	ISOMAP	Isometric Mapping (manifold learning)
LES	Large Eddy Simulation	LF	Low Fidelity
LPV	Linear Parameter-Varying	LSTM	Long Short-Term Memory
LTI	Linear Time-Invariant	MEMS	Micro-Electro-Mechanical Systems
ML	Machine Learning	MLP	Multi-Layer Perceptron
MIMO	Multiple Input Multiple Output	MOR	Model Order Reduction
MPC	Model Predictive Control	NACA	National Advisory Committee for Aeronautics
NIST	National Institute of Standards and Technology	PDE	Partial Differential Equation
PCE	Polynomial Chaos Expansion	pMOR	Parametric Model Order Reduction
PINN	Physics-Informed Neural Network	PINODE	Physics-Informed Neural Ordinary Differential Equation
PARAFAC	Parallel Factor Analysis (tensor decomposition)	POD	Proper Orthogonal Decomposition
QoI	Quantity of Interest	RBF	Radial Basis Function
RB	Reduced Basis	RBM	Reduced Basis Method
RF	Radio Frequency	RHS	Right-Hand Side
ROM	Reduced Order Model	SPD	Symmetric Positive Definite
SPOD	Spectral Proper Orthogonal Decomposition	SUR	Stochastic Uncertainty Reduction
SVD	Singular Value Decomposition	TF	Transfer Function
UQ	Uncertainty Quantification	VAE	Variational Autoencoder

Table 2: List of mathematical symbols.

Symbol	Meaning	Space / Size	Symbol	Meaning	Space / Size
n	Full-order state dimension	\mathbb{N}	n_y	Number of outputs	\mathbb{N}
n_v	Number of inputs	\mathbb{N}	r	Reduced-order state dimension	\mathbb{N}
m	Hyper-reduction sample dimension	\mathbb{N}	μ	Vector of system parameters (e.g. material, geometry etc)	$\mathcal{D} \subset \mathbb{R}^d$
$\mathbf{u}(t, \mu)$	Full-order state vector	\mathbb{R}^n	$\mathbf{y}(t, \mu)$	Observed outputs	\mathbb{R}^{n_y}
$\mathbf{v}_{in}(t, \mu)$	Input vector	\mathbb{R}^{n_v}	f	General system dynamics function	$\mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$
g	General output function	$\mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{n_y}$	\mathbf{E}	Full-order descriptor matrix	$\mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$
\mathbf{A}	Full-order system matrix	$\mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$	\mathbf{B}	Full-order input matrix	$\mathbb{R}^{n \times n_v}$
\mathbf{C}	Full-order output matrix	$\mathbb{R}^{n_y \times n}$	\mathbf{D}	Full-order feed-through matrix	$\mathbb{R}^{n_y \times n_v}$
\mathbf{V}	Trial basis used to project the full-order model onto a reduced subspace	$\mathbf{V} \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times r}$	\mathbf{W}	Test basis used in Petrov-Galerkin projection to evaluate residuals	$\mathbf{W} \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times r}$
$\ \cdot\ _F$	Frobenius norm of a matrix; used to measure matrix size or error	\mathbb{R}	\mathcal{M}	Solution manifold: the set of all states $\mathbf{u}(t, \mu)$ for $t \in [0, T]$ and parameters $\mu \in \mathcal{D}$	$\mathcal{M} \subset \mathbb{R}^n$
N_t	Number of time samples for Snapshot Matrix	\mathbb{N}	N_μ	Number of different parameter samples for Snapshot Matrix	\mathbb{N}
N	Total number of samples for Snapshot Matrix	\mathbb{N}	\mathbf{S}	Snapshot matrix	$\mathbb{R}^{n \times N}$
\mathbf{U}	Left singular vector matrix from SVD	Depends on input matrix size	Σ	Singular value diagonal matrix	Depends on input matrix size

Symbol	Meaning	Space / Size	Symbol	Meaning	Space / Size
\mathbf{Z}	Right singular vector matrix from SVD	Depends on input matrix size	σ	Singular values	\mathbb{R}
ε	Error or tolerance	\mathbb{R}^+	$\hat{\mathbf{E}}$	Reduced-order descriptor matrix	$\mathbb{R}^{r \times r}$
$\hat{\mathbf{A}}$	Reduced-order system matrix	$\mathbb{R}^{r \times r}$	$\hat{\mathbf{B}}$	Reduced-order input matrix	$\mathbb{R}^{r \times n_v}$
$\hat{\mathbf{C}}$	Reduced-order output matrix	$\mathbb{R}^{n_y \times r}$	$\hat{\mathbf{D}}$	Reduced-order feed-through matrix	$\mathbb{R}^{n_y \times n_v}$
\mathbf{V}_0	Reference orthonormal basis used for alignment (Procrustes) or as the base point in manifold interpolation	$\mathbf{V}_0 \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times r}$	$SO(r)$	Special orthogonal group; the set of all $r \times r$ rotation matrices with unit determinant	$SO(r) \subset \mathbb{R}^{r \times r}$
\mathbf{Q}	Orthogonal (rotation) matrix from the Procrustes alignment problem	$SO(r) \subset \mathbb{R}^{r \times r}$	$\tilde{\mathbf{A}}$	Congruence-transformed system matrix	$\mathbb{R}^{r \times r}$
$\tilde{\mathbf{B}}$	Congruence-transformed input matrix	$\mathbb{R}^{r \times n_v}$	$\tilde{\mathbf{C}}$	Congruence-transformed output matrix	$\mathbb{R}^{n_y \times r}$
$\tilde{\mathbf{D}}$	Direct feed-through matrix, typically unchanged under congruence transformations	$\mathbb{R}^{n_y \times n_v}$	$\tilde{\mathbf{E}}$	Congruence-transformed descriptor matrix	$\mathbb{R}^{r \times r}$
$\phi_i(\mu)$	Interpolation coefficient for the i -th precomputed reduced matrix or basis	\mathbb{R}	ω_j	Frequency sample point where the system is evaluated	\mathbb{R}
\mathbf{H}	Transfer function of the full-order system. \mathbf{H}_j is at ω_j	$\mathbb{C}^{n_y \times n_v}$	\mathbf{L}_{kj}	Loewner matrix	$\mathbb{C}^{n_y \times n_v}$
$\mathbf{L}_{\sigma, kj}$	Shifted Loewner matrix	$\mathbb{C}^{n_y \times n_v}$	$GL(r)$	Lie group representing all nonsingular linear transformations in r dimensions	$\mathbb{R}^{r \times r}$
P	Controllability Gramian of an LTI system	$\mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$	Q	Observability Gramian of an LTI system	$\mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$
\mathbf{T}_{BT}	Similarity (balancing) transformation for balanced truncation	$\mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$	$\hat{\mathbf{H}}$	Transfer function of ROM	$\mathbb{C}^{n_y \times n_v}$
\mathbf{L}_c	Low-rank Cholesky factor of the controllability Gramian	$\mathbb{R}^{n \times \ell}$	\mathbf{L}_o	Low-rank Cholesky factor of the observability Gramian: $Q \approx \mathbf{L}_o \mathbf{L}_o^\top$	$\mathbb{R}^{n \times \ell}$
\mathcal{H}_2	\mathcal{H}_2 -norm of an LTI system; measures the RMS gain from input to output over all frequencies	\mathbb{R}	\mathcal{H}_{inf}	\mathcal{H}_{∞} -norm of an LTI system; maximum gain over all frequencies	\mathbb{R}
γ_j	Shift parameter used in ADI iteration to compute low-rank Cholesky factors	\mathbb{R} (scalar, $j = 1, \dots, \ell$)	ℓ	Number of columns (rank) of low-rank Cholesky factors of Gramians	\mathbb{N}
$G(n, \ell)$	Grassmann manifold of ℓ -dimensional subspaces of \mathbb{R}^n .	Set of ℓ -dimensional subspaces in \mathbb{R}^n	$\mathcal{K}_{r, \ell}$	Krylov subspace spanned by the first r_ℓ moments in moment-matching ROMs	$\mathbb{R}^{n \times r_\ell}$
r_ℓ	Number of moments matched in a Krylov-type ROM	\mathbb{N}	s_ℓ	Expansion points (shifts) used in Krylov/moment-matching methods	\mathbb{C}
$\hat{\lambda}_\ell$	Poles of the system used as expansion points in IRKA	\mathbb{C}	θ	Coefficient in the affine decomposition of parametrized operators	\mathbb{R}
$\mathbf{r}(\mu^*)$	Galerkin residual evaluated at parameter μ^*	\mathbb{R}^n	Δ	Efficient upper bound on the dual-norm of the residual for parameter μ^*	\mathbb{R}
$\mathcal{P}_{\text{train}}$	Set of training parameters where high-fidelity solutions are available	Subset of parameter space \mathcal{D}	\mathbf{U}_m	Collateral basis used in (D)EIM/Hyper-reduction to approximate nonlinear or non-affine operators	$\mathbb{R}^{n \times m}$
\mathbf{P}	Boolean sampling matrix selecting indices of residual or operator entries in DEIM/Hyper-reduction	$\{0, 1\}^{n \times m}$	\mathbf{M}	Mass matrix of a mechanical system	$\mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$
\mathbf{K}	Stiffness matrix of a mechanical system	$\mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$	f	External force (or load) vector	\mathbb{R}^n
\mathbf{q}	Displacement vector of the mechanical system.	\mathbb{R}^n	\mathbf{V}^v	Velocity basis derived from \mathbf{V}^x via $\mathbf{V}^v = \mathbf{M}^{-1} \mathbf{K} \mathbf{V}^x \mathbf{\Lambda}^{-1/2}$	$\mathbb{R}^{n \times r}$
\mathbf{V}^x	Displacement basis obtained from modal analysis (mass-orthonormalized).	$\mathbb{R}^{n \times r}$	$\hat{\mathbf{G}}$	Reduced Hamiltonian (energy) matrix in the structure-preserving ROM	$\mathbb{R}^{2r \times 2r}$
\mathbf{T}_2	Stacked basis for structure-preserving ROM: $\mathbf{T}_2 = [\mathbf{V}^x \ \mathbf{V}^v]$	$\mathbb{R}^{n \times 2r}$	$H(\bar{\mathbf{z}})$	Hamiltonian function representing the total energy	\mathbb{R}
$\hat{\mathbf{J}}$	Reduced symplectic structure matrix (Hamiltonian pair) in the ROM	$\mathbb{R}^{2r \times 2r}$	$\mathbf{D}(s)$	Denominator factor of a coprime factorization of the transfer function.	$\mathbb{R}^{n_v \times n_v}$
$\mathbf{N}(s)$	Numerator factor of a coprime factorization of the transfer function.	$\mathbb{R}^{n_y \times n_v}$	\mathbf{X}_i	Tangent vector obtained by mapping the local subspace \mathbf{V}_i to the tangent space $T_{[\mathbf{V}_0]}G(n, r)$ via the Grassmann logarithm; $\mathbf{X}_i = \log_{\mathbf{V}_0}(V_i)$	$\mathbb{R}^{n \times r}$
$T_{[\mathbf{V}_0]}G$	Tangent space of the Grassmann manifold $G(n, r)$ at the reference subspace \mathbf{V}_0	$\mathbb{R}^{n \times r}$			

Symbol	Meaning	Space / Size	Symbol	Meaning	Space / Size
$\mathbf{T}(\mu)$	Interpolated tangent vector in $T_{[\mathbf{V}_0]}G(n, r)$ obtained by blending X_i with weights $w_i(\mu)$	$\mathbb{R}^{n \times r}$	Θ	Diagonal matrix of principal angles between subspaces	$\mathbb{R}^{r \times r}$
$w_k(\mu)$	Smooth weighting functions for local reduced bases, obtained via clustering	\mathbb{R}	\mathcal{D}_k	Subdomain of the parameter space \mathcal{D} used to define local reduced bases	$\subset \mathcal{D}$
\mathbf{V}_k	Local reduced basis constructed from snapshots restricted to the subdomain \mathcal{D}_k	$\mathbb{R}^{n \times r_k}$	$\mathcal{S}(n, r)$	Schubert variety — structured submanifold of the Grassmann manifold representing rank- r subspaces with specific incidence properties	Manifold subset of $\mathcal{G}(n, r)$
I_M	Subspace interpolation map from the parameter domain to the tangent space of the reference subspace	$I_M : \mathcal{D} \rightarrow T[\mathbf{V}_0]G(n, r)$	$\eta_k(\mu)$	Local error indicator for hierarchical POD	$\eta_k(\mu) \in \mathbb{R}$
r_{\min}	Minimum rank used when lifting or truncating local bases to a common dimension for interpolation	$r_{\min} \in \mathbb{N}$	r_{\max}	Maximum rank used when lifting or truncating local bases to a common dimension for interpolation	$r_{\max} \in \mathbb{N}$
$\mathcal{F}_H(\mu)$	High-fidelity model for parameter μ	\mathbb{R}^n	$\mathcal{F}_L(\mu)$	Low-fidelity (fast but approximate) model for parameter μ	\mathbb{R}^n
$\delta(\mu)$	Correction term representing the difference between high- and low-fidelity models	$\delta(\mu) \in \mathbb{R}^n$	\mathbf{V}_L	Reduced basis obtained from snapshots of the low-fidelity model	$V_L \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times r}$
\mathbf{V}_δ	Reduced basis obtained from high-fidelity corrections $\delta(\mu_j^H)$	$V_\delta \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times r_\delta}$	$\delta(\mu_j^H)$	High-fidelity correction evaluated at a specific high-fidelity training parameter μ_j^H	$\delta(\mu_j^H) \in \mathbb{R}^n$
q_α	Physical displacement vector of substructure α	\mathbb{R}^{n_α}	q_α^i	Interior (internal) DOFs of substructure α	$\mathbb{R}^{n_\alpha^i}$
q_α^b	Boundary DOFs of substructure α	$\mathbb{R}^{n_\alpha^b}$	n_α	Total DOFs of substructure α	$n_\alpha^i + n_\alpha^b$
\mathbf{M}_α	Mass matrix of substructure α	$\mathbb{R}^{n_\alpha \times n_\alpha}$	\mathbf{K}_α	Stiffness matrix of substructure α	$\mathbb{R}^{n_\alpha \times n_\alpha}$
$\mathbf{f}_\alpha(t)$	External forcing vector on substructure α	\mathbb{R}^{n_α}	\mathbf{V}_α^i	Fixed-interface vibration modes (interior)	$\mathbb{R}^{n_\alpha^i \times r_\alpha}$
\mathbf{C}_α^i	Static constraint modes mapping boundary to interior DOFs	$\mathbb{R}^{n_\alpha^i \times n_\alpha^b}$	$\hat{\mathbf{q}}_\alpha^i$	Reduced interior coordinates after modal reduction	\mathbb{R}^{r_α}
\mathbf{T}_α	Transformation matrix combining interior modes and constraint modes	$\mathbb{R}^{n_\alpha \times (r_\alpha + n_\alpha^b)}$	$\hat{\mathbf{M}}_\alpha$	Reduced mass matrix after projection	$\mathbb{R}^{(r_\alpha + n_\alpha^b) \times (r_\alpha + n_\alpha^b)}$
$\hat{\mathbf{K}}_\alpha$	Reduced stiffness matrix after projection	$\mathbb{R}^{(r_\alpha + n_\alpha^b) \times (r_\alpha + n_\alpha^b)}$	$\hat{\mathbf{f}}_\alpha^i(t)$	Reduced forcing vector after projection	$\mathbb{R}^{r_\alpha + n_\alpha^b}$
$\phi_i(\mu^*)$	Interpolation weights for parameter-dependent operators	\mathbb{R}	S_α	Subdomain / substructure α	N/A
Ω_0	Reference finite-element mesh	Mesh nodes in \mathbb{R}^d	$\Omega(\mu)$	Deformed mesh corresponding to parameter μ	Mesh nodes in \mathbb{R}^d
x_0	Reference node in Ω_0	\mathbb{R}^d	$\Psi(x_0, \mu)$	Mapping from reference mesh to deformed mesh	$\mathbb{R}^d \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^d$
x	Deformed position of node corresponding to x_0	\mathbb{R}^d	$v_j(x, \mu)$	Transported POD mode defined on deformed mesh $\Omega(\mu)$	\mathbb{R}^n
\mathbf{V}^0	Reference POD basis on Ω_0	$\mathbb{R}^{n \times r}$	$\Phi_\alpha(\mu)$	Multivariate polynomial basis function in gPC expansion	Scalar
$c_{i,\alpha}$	Coefficient of gPC expansion for reduced coordinate i	Scalar	\mathbf{Z}	Boolean selector for hyper-reduction	$\{0, 1\}^{ \Omega \times m}$
p	Maximum polynomial degree in gPC expansion	\mathbb{N}	r	Dimension of the reduced basis (number of retained modes)	\mathbb{N}
S	Online speed-up: ratio of full-order model runtime to reduced-order model runtime	Scalar	t_{on}	Online query / evaluation cost	Scalar (time)
t_{off}	Offline training / basis construction cost	Scalar (time)	ϵ_y	Relative error in the quantity of interest	Scalar
ϵ_x	Relative error in the state vector	Scalar			

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